

Hierarchical Phenomena in Multicomponent Liquids: Simulation Methods, Analysis, Chemistry

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Received Date
Accepted Date

DOI: 00.0000/xxxxxxxxxx

Complex, multicomponent, solutions have often been studied solely through the lens of specific applications of interest. Yet advances to both simulation methodologies (enhanced sampling, etc.) and analysis techniques (network analysis algorithms and others), are creating a trove of data that reveal transcending characteristics across vast compositional phase space. This perspective discusses technical considerations of the reliable and accurate simulations of complex solutions, followed by the advances to analysis algorithms that elucidate coupling of different length and timescale behavior (hierarchical phenomena). The different manifestations of hierarchical phenomena are presented across an array of solution environments, emphasizing fundamental and ongoing science questions. With a more advanced molecular understanding in hand, a quintessential application (solvent extraction) is discussed, where significant opportunities exist to re-imagine the technical scope of an established technology.

1 Introduction

The ubiquity of multicomponent liquids cannot be understated; pervasive in our everyday lives, chemical synthesis (both biologically and by human hand) and the different stages of the technology lifecycle. From a chemical or engineering perspective, many theoretical paradigms exist to predict and describe the physicochemical properties of such complex solutions—some with their foundations in the historical beginnings of alchemical science.¹ Still, the theoretical bridge that traverses molecular scale interactions of solutes and solvent to fluid dynamics and equations of state, has many pillars left unplaced. It has only been within the last decade that molecular simulation infrastructure (including software, algorithms, force fields, etc.) and structural analyses have advanced to the stage where robust study of compositional phase space can be pursued. Molecular simulation of “realistic solutions” has further inspired development of new analyses that move beyond typical pairwise correlations; methods that borrow from topological algebra and geometry to create a hierarchical perspective of solution speciation, collective organization and dynamics. At the same time, advances to experimental in-situ measurement and the length and timescales that probe solution

speciation and properties are beginning to align with the conditions measurable by simulation techniques. Finally, as this data builds, uncertainty quantification can begin to be considered. All of these events portend the onset of a paradigm shift in chemical understanding and theoretical description of complex, multicomponent, liquids.

It is becoming apparent that there are many transcending characteristics of complex solutions across vastly different compositions. One attribute is that the equilibrium and/or nonequilibrium physicochemical properties cannot be described in the absence of many body effects. Though they may be associated with the fundamental description of energies of interaction, many body effects may also emerge from very simple pairwise interactions at a local level that lead to significant complexity as larger length and timescales are studied. A natural outcome is the close coupling of different length and timescale behavior. Though such a statement could be made even for pure water,² in multicomponent systems the degrees of freedom are increased dramatically: local organization of solutes into a supramolecular assembly can then create a percolated network of aggregated assemblies that in turn supports a phase transition.³ Or, in a concentrated electrolyte, the local motions of water are coupled to longer length scale dynamics of evolving ion solvation networks.⁴ The collective organization of the solution across different length scales and the dynamic motion across time-scales, challenges study of the features of the underlying free energy landscape (minima and barriers) that directs reaction outcomes, kinetics of motion and reactions, and phase behavior.⁵ In order to truly understand multicomponent complex solutions, both the local and global descrip-

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† Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: [details of any supplementary information available should be included here]. See DOI: 10.1039/cXCP00000x/

tion of the system is relevant.

This article is *not* a review, instead we are motivated to emphasize and contribute to the change in philosophical perspective that has emerged recently in the literature. A perspective that is elevating complex solution chemistry from the application domain to an understanding of fundamental science that recognizes and leverages similarities in behavior and properties—whether the solutions are molten salts, aqueous electrolytes, molecular organic solutions, or microemulsions. The problem is viewed through the lens of molecular simulations, the properties and knowledge gained therein and integrated with appropriate experimental techniques. What are the molecular simulation challenges to effectively probe complex solutions across length and timescale? Once a simulation is performed, how can different analysis paradigms reveal new insight and how generalizable are those observations across vastly different solution systems? An emphasis is also made upon the concept of hierarchical phenomena in complex solutions. What is an appropriate framework to seamlessly describe local and non-local behavior? What is the language that we use to describe heterogeneity of solution structure, microenvironments and rare events that may be essential to describe an observable of interest? These questions are propositioned with examples from our own work and related literature. With these fundamental science questions now articulated, we loop back to an application that epitomizes virtually all aspects of solution phase complexity, solvent extraction, and demonstrate how this separations technology is being revolutionized by an emergent understanding of hierarchical phenomena in multicomponent liquids.

2 Sampling the Energy Landscape

The simulation of complex solutions is an interesting challenge to the method that describes inter- and intramolecular interactions and defines the potential energy landscape (either classically or quantum mechanically). It imposes a high demand upon sampling the landscape to create an ensemble distribution of configurations at equilibrium that is analogous to the experimental distribution (as determined by comparison to experimental observation). The "system conditions" within experiment can be quite different relative to simulation—whether the composition of the solution, or the time and length scales of experimental measurement. Open acknowledgment and discussion of the limitations of approximations made within the simulation protocol, or in the comparison of simulation and experiment, supports candid comparisons and the development of more robust chemical models and a deeper understanding. This section focuses upon specific challenges that arise from the many body interactions and multidimensional correlations found in complex solutions. It presents a practical perspective of the techniques that increase reliability of simulation data and enhance sampling of the energy/configurational landscape. Section 3 focuses upon the complementary analyses that elucidate such correlations and openly points to the question of the level of fidelity to which we can interpret simulation data.

2.1 Representation of the Potential Energy

The analytical form of the Hamiltonian and the manner by which the associated energy landscape is sampled are often intertwined because of considerations of computational cost. Classical force field representations of the potential energy can be remarkably effective at reproducing the behavior of complex solutions, however issues of transferability, sensitivity to force field parameters, and many body effects or polarization can manifest themselves in unexpected ways. Alternatively, with "ab initio" molecular dynamics methods (AIMD), one can compute the forces acting on the nuclei from electronic structure calculations performed "on-the-fly" as the molecular dynamics trajectory is generated (dynamical evolution of the nuclei is commonly propagated using classical mechanics). In this way, the electronic variables are not integrated out beforehand, but are considered as active degrees of freedom. This implies that the approximation is shifted from the level of selecting the model potential (force-field) to the level of selecting a particular approximation for solving the Schrödinger equation. Yet the AIMD framework suffers from poor configurational sampling capabilities at longer length and timescales. Thus, an iterative scheme that couples configurational sampling from classical MD to investigate short time and lengthscale behavior using AIMD is often employed to both learn about specific effects of electronic structure upon local geometries and dynamics, as well as for force field benchmarking.^{6,7}

The fidelity of simulations employing empirical potentials often depends on the applicability of the empirical fitting to the simulated system. Simulations far from the conditions under which the empirical potentials were fit could result in unphysical behavior.⁸ Similarly, condensed phase force fields are often developed for specific high dielectric environments, e.g., pure water. Parameters such as partial atomic charges, developed in this way are not as accurate for application to low dielectric phases. Practical approaches have been developed to improve the transferability of classical, nonpolarizable potentials to diverse, nonideal, solutions conditions. One such approach is charge scaling of ionic species with integer formal charges to improve the accuracy of ion-ion interactions in condensed phases.^{9–11} Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov found that optimal charge scaling corrections correspond to a factor of $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_{el}}$, where ϵ_{el} is the electronic dielectric.⁹ For water, where $\epsilon_{el}=1.78$, this corresponds to scaling charged species by ≈ 0.7 . Following this approach, Vega and coworkers developed "Madrid model" monovalent and divalent ion potentials using charge scaling for a range of ions and ionic strength for use with TIP4P/2005 water.^{12,13}

Similarly, charge scaling can be applied to neutral species, although the appropriate degree of scaling is generally less⁹ because condensed phase corrections are built into partial charge calculations¹⁴ and neutral species are not constrained to have integer total charge. Often, diffusion of charged or amphiphilic species are substantially underestimated by force fields lacking explicit polarization.¹⁵ Similar charge scaling approaches have been implemented to address this force field limitation, including for ionic liquids¹⁶ and amphiphiles.¹⁷

There have been substantial recent efforts in the development

of force fields with explicit polarization which naturally improve transferability to complex solutions. One such force field is AMOEBA, where a multipole expansion of the point electrostatics is combined with an induced dipole.^{18–23} Another force field approach, TCPE, also uses a point multipole expansion with an induced dipole contribution in addition to a hydrogen bond term.²⁴ These potentials have also been applied to model heavy elements in aqueous environments.^{25–28} A similar energy decomposition approach for fitting classical potentials to QM data is the NEMO approach with Gagliardi and coworkers have also extended to develop actinide-water potentials.^{29,30} Simulation times of 10 ns or so are achievable with these polarizable force fields for relatively small periodic systems, allowing for highly accurate and well-sampled structural and dynamical data for aqueous solutions.

Other approaches exist for delivering a compromise between the efficiency of pairwise additive force fields and the effects of electronic polarization. Monatomic ions with integer formal charges can have high charge densities, which result in strong ion-induced dipole interactions which are challenging to model in such force fields.⁹ As a result, force fields with 12-6 plus electrostatic-type nonbonded potentials can be fitted to a target thermodynamic property, but not generally multiple properties of interest simultaneously. To address this, Li, Song and Merz, Jr. developed 12-6-4 plus electrostatic nonbonded potentials for a broad range of monatomic ions with different valencies^{31–33} which capture ion-oxygen distance, solvation free energy and coordination number simultaneously, representing a substantial improvement over existing 12-6 potentials.

As discussed above, while the CMD equilibrium ensemble can reproduce a variety of physicochemical properties of a complex solution, that does not necessarily mean that the force field can capture all of the physics one would consider important. Like any method, CMD can rely upon cancellation of errors, yet in complex solutions, this can be highly unpredictable. Error cancellation influences both the choice of the force field parameters as well as the properties that the force field is benchmarked against. Here, we provide three examples that illustrate counter-intuitive results that derive from error cancellation that is imparted by competitive interactions within a force field due to the complexity of interactions in multicomponent solutions.

Example 1: Water Orientation at an Interface. Error cancellation has the interesting ability to negate the impact of substantial changes to a force field. In an example that studied surfactant-laden liquid/liquid interfaces, Clark and coworkers investigated force field modulation of the hydrophilicity of tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) through charge scaling, on the interfacial properties of a water/*n*-hexane interface.³⁴ While properties such as interfacial tension and interfacial width were found to be sensitive to charge scaling for scaling factors of 0.7 and 0.9, certain other interfacial properties were not affected. The unaffected properties include interfacial water orientation. Contributions to water orientation relative to the interfacial plane are opposite for water which are hydrogen bonded to the surfactant and those which are not. Surfactant adsorption increases the populations of both of those interfacial water species, through direct interaction with surface water and induced roughness which exposes

more interfacial area. The result is that, for the same number of adsorbed surfactant molecules, the net water orientation is relatively consistent between surfactant models. Therefore, interpretation of simulation results on the basis of water orientation should be performed with caution. For example, favorable comparison with experimental data which measures interfacial water dipole³⁵ might not guarantee realistic surfactant behavior as other interfacial properties could vary substantially—with varying degrees of accuracy—between force fields which yield similar interfacial water net orientation.

Example 2: Water-Ion Interactions. Force fields with sophisticated functional forms to describe interaction potentials, such as AMOEBA, rely on error cancellation in parameterization to capture interactions energetics, such as water-water or water-ion dimers. Mao et al. performed energy decomposition analysis on such interactions for a range of ion types to understand the impact of different energy contributions on the excellent agreement of the AMOEBA force field with QM data.³⁶ They found that short-range interactions, being harder to model with even with a 14-7 plus multipole expansion representation of electrostatics, featured significant error cancellation to account for charge penetration and charge transfer. For example, the H-O...O angle dependence of the energy of a water dimer is correctly modeled by AMOEBA through error cancellation. Reduced 14-7 repulsion relative to QM data is offset by AMOEBA underpredicted the favorable electrostatic interaction. The result is excellent agreement across the range of H-O...O angles. Similar error cancellation was found for water-halide interactions. At short distances the underestimated favorable H₂O...Cl[−] electrostatic interaction (relative to QM data) was compensated for by overestimated polarization. Conversely, for H₂O...F[−], the favorability of both electrostatic and van der Waals interactions at short range compound, rather than cancel. This results in noticeable deviation of the AMOEBA H₂O...F[−] PES from the QM data, while the H₂O...Cl[−] PES shows excellent agreement.

Example 3: Non-unique Contributions to Atom-Atom Correlations. Radial distribution functions (RDFs), can be obtained experimentally from elastic total scattering experiments (X-ray or neutron), and are often employed to probe solution structure via interpretation of the atom-atom correlations that contribute within certain distance regimes. In simple solutions the unique interatomic pairwise distances are generally well-separated. Yet as solution complexity (or the degrees of freedom of different interatomic interactions) increases, the likelihood of overlapping pairwise distance distributions also increases. This issue is not generally quantified, as it requires detailed subensemble analysis of atomistic simulations—preferably integrated with experimental measurement (see Section 3). Predicted pairwise distances are incredibly sensitive to both representation of interatomic interactions, and further, the competition of interactions in local environments. Concentrated electrolytes are an excellent platform to compare the influence of force field representation and competitive interactions upon the contributions of atom-atom correlations.

In the case of concentrated NaOH_(aq), X-ray data is predominated by Na...O, O...O, and Na...Na correlations, while neutron

scattering reveals information about the structural positions of D- (or H-) containing species and their intermolecular interactions. Traditional polarizable and non-polarizable classical potentials are not able to match the primary features of the observed data, while a neural network fitted potential yields better agreement.⁴ Yet the underpinning intermolecular interactions and distribution of local solvation environments about OH⁻, Na⁺, and H₂O have unanticipated variations that in turn impact distance dependencies in interesting ways. For example, the OH⁻ H-atom interactions with the H-atoms of H₂O are highly dependent upon force field implementation, suggesting that the orientational correlations are highly sensitive to intermolecular interaction. The associated RDF for this atom-pair is predicted to have a bimodal distribution by a non-polarizable potential, while both polarizable and neural network potentials exhibit a single peak, but at different distances (neither of which agrees well with experiment). Further, when comparing the atom-atom correlations between the concentrated NaOH_(aq) and that of pure water, both the polarizable and non-polarizable potentials predict significant perturbations of the water-water correlations that do not appear in the neural network fitted potential.

2.2 Finite Size Effects

Inherent to simulations with periodic boundary conditions are finite size effects, which can manifest themselves in a myriad of ways that all derive from the fact that the size of the simulation box employed alters the fundamental energy landscape relative to the experimental system. A common instance occurs in simulations with interfaces present between two bulk phases. In a real (experimental) system, the fraction of molecules in either phase occupying the interface is essentially zero. However, due to the limitations in simulation length scale, analogous simulations often only include the first several nm of a bulk liquid phase from the interface. As a result, a substantial fraction of the total molecules in each phase are interfacial, with the exact amount depending on the unit cell geometry and size. This artifact of multiphase systems can impact the energetics of the system. For example, the presence of an interface between two solvents which are only partially miscible increases the simulated solubility in the finite simulation relative to a larger simulation unit cell or analogous (but interface-free) grand canonical or Gibbs ensemble simulation.³⁷

In another example, finite size effects can change the bulk concentration of a particular component by causing the formation of regions that have enhanced or reduced concentration within the simulation unit cell. This finite size effect is also present in interfacial simulations, where the bulk phase concentration of surface-active components of either phase becomes depleted, reducing the effective concentration of in that bulk phase. To address this problem, constant μ ensemble simulations can be implemented instead to generate interfaces between mutually saturated alcohol/water phases to investigate interfacial properties.^{38,39} This can also occur when studying low concentration effects of self-associating solutions where, in order to form aggregates of a particular species in solution, the effective con-

centration of that species changes significantly as the aggregate depletes the simulation box of that species' total concentration. In this case, careful treatment of finite size effects is necessary to obtain statistically meaningful aggregation ensemble average properties. Kindt and coworkers developed methods to quantify aggregation of monomers and explicitly account for depletion of the bulk monomer concentration.⁴⁰ By considering the partition of all possible s-mer configurations for a fixed N total monomers, Kindt proposed a method to extrapolate the results of aggregation in finite systems to the large N limit. This approach can, for example, be applied to determine association constants for critical nucleation clusters, avoiding biased simulation methods typically employed when studying rare events.⁴¹ This approach has since been applied to accurately compute aggregation free energies and critical micelle concentrations from relatively small simulations.^{42,43}

2.3 Ergodicity in Complex Solutions

Although traditional molecular dynamics methods are often used to study complex solutions, there are certain regimes, where—due to major collective motions (self-assembly), high viscosity, or position on a phase diagram—ergodicity cannot be assumed. A significant challenge with complex solutions is that there can be large variation in timescales of the phenomena of interest. Local speciation may equilibrate on the several ns scale, whereas interfacial properties may equilibrate on the 10's of ns scale (e.g., liquid/liquid interfacial tension), and the formation of large assemblies (clustering or aggregation) can evolve on the 100's of ns scale. Consider recent work on organic solutions of metal-ligand complexes that assemble into aggregates at high concentration.⁴⁴ Figure 1 presents the metal...metal radial distribution function (RDF) of the component metal-ligand (ML) complexes, where small clusters of interacting ML species form after nanoseconds, whereas much larger dense aggregates begin to evolve after 10s of ns.

In the case where ergodicity is not easily achieved via simple temperature ramping/cooling, extended timescale simulations, or cycling of alternate ensembles, several recent reviews provide significant detail about the many methods to accelerate sampling on an energy landscape to create an equilibrium ensemble or obtain good statistics of rare event processes.^{45–47} In this context, are those methods that employ collective variables to accelerate sampling along specific pathways on an energy landscape, those that perturb the effective energy landscape upon which the system evolves to increase the likelihood of overcoming barriers or creating random walks on the surface (e.g., tempering methods), or combinations of these traditional approaches. Unlike biomolecular simulations, where there may be a few key collective variables (CVs) that can be employed to overcome barriers on an energy landscape, self-assembly or phase behavior of complex solutions as a whole generally have no such simplified representations.^{5,48} As such, CV based sampling schemes are generally not applicable unless specific reactive processes occurring within a complex solution are to be studied. It has been observed generally that even simple reactions in solution can have a free energy path

Fig. 1 The uranium-uranium RDF for 0.25 M $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{TBP})_2$ metal-ligand complexes in n-dodecane for various time ranges of a single trajectory.⁴⁴ The local organization (up to 2 nm) equilibrate quickly, while the long-range correlation (2 to 5 nm) has a longer relaxation time. Reprinted under the creative commons licence from Servis, M. J. and Wu, D. T. and Shafer, J. C. and Clark, A. Reimagining Third Phase Formation as the Miscibility Gap of a Molecular Solution, 2019, ChemRxiv DOI:10.26434/chemrxiv.10060253.v1

that is highly dependent upon solvent degrees of freedom.^{5,49} As such, there is growing interest in developing CVs that can capture higher dimensionality features than simple geometric parameters or combinations thereof. This has the potential of avoiding so-called "hidden barriers" when using CV based methods, those barriers that occur along different directions of the reduced dimensionality energy landscape provided when using a CV. The following section discusses recent advances in collective variables that capture the collective motions of solvents and solutes that can occur in complex solutions.

2.4 Chemical Transformations

Chemical transformations can be thought of in two distinct ways; on the one hand, the energy differences between different thermodynamic initial and final states may be solely of interest, while on the other hand, the entire reaction pathway—which includes the barrier for transformation—may be needed. In its simplest representation, the energy difference between two states A and B can be computed from the Zwanzig relationship:⁵⁰

$$\Delta F_{A \rightarrow B} = -k_b T \ln \langle e^{-\frac{M_i}{k_b T}} \rangle. \quad (1)$$

Although the direct calculation of the free energy difference suffers from significant issues, including sufficient sampling and error minimization, many methods have been developed to achieve reliable free energy differences. These methods, in a simplistic description, create a thermodynamic connection between states A and B, by creating overlapping distributions of configura-

tions between them. Such techniques includes the Bennett Acceptance Ratio (BAR) method⁵¹ and the now widely used multistate variant (MBAR),⁵² as well as free energy perturbation (FEP),^{50,53} and thermodynamic integration (TI).^{53–55} These methods are all effective at determining properties of complex solutions like partition coefficients between two phases.^{56,57} In principle, solubility can also be measured in this manner, for example, using the pseudosupercritical path integration (PSPi) method, which determines the free energy difference between a common reference state and the species in the crystalline and solution phases. A weakly interacting fluid phase is used, where the strength of interactions between the molecules is gradually reduced in such a way that the free energy is continuous along the path. This method was used to study the solubility limit of NaCl in water and light alcohols.⁵⁸

The different task of identifying relevant reaction coordinates in complex solutions is a challenge. Employing an oversimplified reaction coordinate can result in a misleadingly free-energy landscape with lower barriers and wrong activation states and kinetics. The evolution of a chemical reaction is often mediated, or even driven, by collective motions of the atoms/molecules, and their molecular environment.⁵⁹ Reaction coordinates of higher dimensionality are paramount to account for correlated motions along a chemical transformation pathway influenced by several intertwined molecular degrees of freedom. For example, the seemingly simple dissociation/association of the NaCl ion pair, which has been studied using the ion-ion distance as the intuitive reaction coordinate, needs to include solvent degrees of freedom in the formulation of an accurate reaction coordinate.⁶⁰ Along with the solvent structure, solvent dynamics around ion pairs can play a crucial role in the rates of ionic transformations. The fate of the activated states of ionic reactions (i.e., alkali metal cations and halogen anions) can be correlated to fluctuations in the ion-water coordination number.⁶¹ In addition to the coordination number, the role of the number of bridging waters,^{48,62} and the number density of the water molecules around the ions^{48,63} can drive chemical transformations.

Mathematical functions with specific symmetry properties have been used as collective variables to represent molecular transformations that involve symmetry-breaking fluctuations (i.e., center of mass ($S_p^{(1)}$) or inertia tensors ($S_p^{(2)}$) fluctuations):

$$S_p^{(1)} = \sum_{i \in S} \frac{1}{r_i^p} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i}{r_i} \quad (2a)$$

$$S_p^{(2)} = \sum_{i \in S} \frac{1}{r_i^p} \frac{r_i^2 \mathbb{I} - 3\mathbf{r}_i \otimes \mathbf{r}_i}{r_i^2} \quad (2b)$$

These have been used in combination with molecular dynamics to study the effect of symmetric concerted motions in ion mobility mechanisms.⁶⁴ As another example, consider the ion transport through a liquid-liquid interface. The effective transfer of an ion between two phases can occur through the formation/breaking of a water finger like structure. The ubiquitous "water finger"-mediated interfacial transport processes has been studied in terms of a collective variable on the basis of the hydrogen-bond connec-

tivity using a graph theoretical approach (see Sect. 4.3).^{65,66}

Searching for appropriate collective coordinates for solution chemical reactions is generally done by trial and error, and relies mostly upon intuition and knowledge about the chemical process under study. Recently, automated approaches to find suitable reaction coordinate through rigorous optimization techniques have also been developed.⁶⁷ The optimization of a given collective variable is referenced to the committor probability: \mathbf{p} (the probabilities for the trajectory, launched from a proper transition state structure, of reaching the reactant or product basins should be equal).^{68,69} A given multiparameter functional form is pre-assigned to the reaction coordinate function which is variationally optimized until the function behaves similar to \mathbf{p} . Other methods for discovering highly dimensional reaction coordinates include (a) Kramers-Langer-Berezhevskii-Szabo (KLBS) theory, which provides an overdamped counterpart to Variational Transition State Theory (VTST); (b) likelihood maximization (using path sampling data to automatically mix, optimize, and test linear combinations of thousands of trial order parameters as reaction coordinates); (c) Inertial likelihood maximization (iLMax) (obtain reaction coordinates with high transmission coefficients and accurate committor models by optimizing models of the reaction probability),⁵ (d) harmonic linear discriminant analysis (HLDA) and variational approach to conformational dynamics (VAC), (e) Machine Learning approaches, generic neural network (GNN),⁷⁰ (f) eigenfunctions that emerge from Markov State Models (MSM) and (g) dimensionality reduction techniques,⁵ principle component analysis (PCA),⁷¹ diffusion maps, isomap,⁷² sketch-map,⁷³ and full correlation analysis.

Summary

The reliable prediction of local and macroscopic properties of complex solutions and the reactions that occur within them, mandates a significant breadth of methodological and theoretical competency. Developments over the last several years have helped to overcome the challenges of incorporating the correct physics in the model representations, sampling of the ensemble distribution, and exploring rare events to create a holistic understanding of the energy landscape and collective motions of solvent and solutes in reaction mechanisms. Yet these methods are an active area of research, where their accuracy has not necessarily been tested across a range of solution systems. Within a specific chemical system, not only should normal benchmarking to relevant experimental data be performed, but significant testing of approximations made in the computational protocol (force field dependence, ergodicity, finite size effects, etc.) is mandated.

3 Analyzing Solution Structure and Speciation

3.1 Traditional Order Parameters

There are several different philosophies aimed at understanding the local structure and dynamics within complex solutions. On the one hand, the specific geometric/organizational features

of individual molecules can be monitored over time to identify key changes in geometry related to reactivity or to create spatial time correlation functions. Local geometry/organization can be quantified using any number of so-called order parameters. Those based upon specific geometric parameters like atom-atom distances and angles are often system dependent. For example, to understand the local structure of solvation about water and characterize its behavior under different conditions, the orientational and translational tetrahedral order parameters,^{74–80} and local structure indices,⁸¹ have been incredibly useful. Another prevalent metric is the coordination number, which represents the number of contacts between two groups of atoms and is defined as $\sum_{i \in A} \sum_{j \in B} s_{ij}$ where s_{ij} is a continuous function of atoms connectivities:

$$s_{ij} = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{r_{ij} - d_0}{r_0}\right)^n}{1 - \left(\frac{r_{ij} - d_0}{r_0}\right)^m} \quad (3)$$

where s_{ij} is 1 if the contact between i and j is formed, zero otherwise (r_{ij} represents the distance between atom i and j).

A complementary suite of methods utilize geometric partitioning to analyze local density or inhomogeneities of solutions.^{82–85} Voronoi analysis is incredibly useful in this regard, as a general approach that may include tessellation, or analysis of fixed volumes of voronoi cells.⁸¹ Tessellation of 3-dimensional space is achieved by using the center of mass of molecules as points that form the center of a sphere. As the radius of the sphere is increased, neighboring spheres intersect and form faces of a voronoi cell (or polyhedron). The volume of the voronoi polyhedron can be related to the free volume of the molecule, and the reciprocal volume is a metric of the local density about the molecule. Different characterization metrics of the voronoi polyhedra have also been developed, for example, the asphericity of the voronoi cell η defined below has been used to characterized the structure of water⁸¹

$$\eta = \frac{A^3}{36\pi V^2} \quad (4)$$

where V and A are, respectively, the volume and area of the polyhedron. η values range from 1 for a perfect sphere to 2.25 for ice Ih and 3.31 for a regular tetrahedron.

These represent a small sample of different order parameters that have been developed to study solutions, and a thorough canvass of all methods, their strengths and weaknesses would likely require its own publication. Yet as our ability to perform reliable simulations of complex solution environments has increased, so too have efforts to create metrics of structure and dynamics that can more seamlessly traverse local vs. global characteristics. In this vein we discuss two related approaches, those analyses based upon the topology of graphs of intermolecular interactions (intermolecular networks), and 3D organizational features that are described using persistent homology. Both approaches borrow from the field of computational topology, which has seen dramatic increases to interdisciplinary applications and mathematical development in the last decade.⁸⁶

3.2 Characterization based upon the topology of intra- or intermolecular graphs

Intermolecular network theory (also referred to as connectedness theory) within chemistry has an aim to determine the relationships between the topological properties of interactions in a chemical system and its physicochemical properties (Figure 2). The analysis of inter- and intramolecular networks of interactions have played a vital role in understanding simple solutions, including hydrogen bond networks of water,^{87,88} solvation of ions,⁸⁹ and the use of percolation theory to understand critical phenomena.^{90–93} To begin using such methods, one must first identify the type of network most relevant to the property of interest, this includes choice of nodes in the network (be they atoms, molecules, or even clusters or coarse grained representations) and the edges that connect them (the criterion to define a specific interaction, using a geometric, or energetic, or probabilistic definition). Several works discuss the details of different aspects of network construction, including the nuances needed to study dynamic changes to networks.^{94,95} Here we focus upon different topological descriptors that reveal information associated with the hierarchical organization, dynamics and phase phenomena.

In this context, we can study chemical networks by representing the molecular interactions as graphs. Graphs are represented through the adjacency matrix, where two “nodes” (or vertices) are said to be connected through edges if they are “adjacent,” where “adjacent” could be related to the strength of a molecular interaction in a chemical context. For simple graphs (i.e., undirected and unweighted graphs), the adjacency matrix is the $n \times n$ square matrix of a graph with n vertices, where each matrix element is defined as:

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n_i \text{ and } n_j \text{ are 'adjacent'} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

PageRank and related eigenvalue metrics of the adjacency matrix of the network, have been shown to represent the complex, 3-dimensional, shapes of molecules, and as such be able to recognize key changes to topology along a reaction pathway.⁹⁶ Further, the forces of these graph theoretic indices in cartesian space has been mapped so as to make that index a collective variable to study reactivity.⁴⁹ The PageRank (PR) index of a given network node k in a unique molecular environment (see full description of PR reformulation for applications in chemical systems by Zhou et al.⁴⁹) is described using the following formula:

$$PR(k) = \frac{1-d}{N} + d \sum_{j \in M\{k\}} \frac{w_{kj}}{W_j} PR(j) \quad (6)$$

where N is the total number of nodes in the graph (i.e., atoms included in the studied molecular graph), $M\{k\}$ is the set of nodes that links to node k , d is a damping factor (between 0 and 1), and $W_j = \sum_i w_{kj}$ is the total weight of all the connections that starts from node j .

Using such a weighted adjacency matrix construction, the Fourier transform of the PR velocity autocorrelation function yields characteristic information about the vibrational and rotational fluctuations, where the frequencies are weighted by the in-

fluence of these fluctuations upon the change in edge weights.⁴⁹ At the same time, the continuity of PR supports its use as a collective variable for a chemical process that could span a highly dimensional energy surface. This was demonstrated for ion-pairing processes in water, where a projection of the biased PR coordinate onto the inter-ion distance resulted in a 3D r -PR energy landscape that illustrated non-linear correlations (Figure 3). Certain portions of reaction had significant solvent reorganization, in which case PR had a large contribution to the mass-weighted minimum energy path (MEP). In other regions, distance alone contributed to the MEP.

While many phenomena of complex solutions, such as speciation, can be understood largely through local structures, other organization occurs over larger length scales. Connectivity in many solutions, such as hydrogen bonding in bulk liquid water under ambient conditions, forms a system-spanning network. Quantifying organization across those larger length scales requires unique analyses. As with speciation, where graph theory is utilized to understand local connectivity patterns, graph theory can also be applied to understand organization of chemical networks over larger length scales. Global metrics of connectivity can be applied to understand the transition from local to macroscopic (or in a periodic simulation, infinite) clustering. Such a transition can be modeled with percolation theory, which is further discussed in the context of phase phenomena in Sect. 4.2. Here, we discuss the application of geodesic analysis to extended chemical networks.

The geodesic distance between two nodes in a connected component is defined as the shortest path between them in that component. For unweighted, undirected graphs, the average geodesic distance of a connected component, a , is defined as

$$a = \sum_{i,j \in C} \frac{d(i,j)}{n(n-1)}, \quad (7)$$

where $d(s,t)$ is the geodesic distance between nodes i and j in connected component C having n total nodes. The factor of $n-1$ scales the average to facilitate comparison between connected components of different size. The average geodesic distance is a measure of compactness and interconnectivity of a network. Alternatively, the eccentricity of a connected component is a measure of its maximum spread. The eccentricity is the largest distance between any pair of nodes, defined as

$$e = \frac{\max_{i,j \in C} d(i,j)}{n-1}. \quad (8)$$

Wang et al. applied geodesic distance, in conjunction with Euclidean distance, to characterize the hydrogen bonded network of a water and mixture alcohol in a confined environments.⁹⁷ The comparison of geodesic distance and Euclidean distance for bulk water and water confined in silicalite-1 showed that the confined water had longer (in real space distance) contiguous hydrogen bonding networks for the same geodesic path length. With tools such as the geodesic distance, the differences in compactness of networks of physical interactions, including hydrogen bonding networks, in different environments can be quantified.

The interconnectedness of the network as a whole can be mea-

Fig. 2 Example workflow for topological analysis of networks of intermolecular interactions, with example topological analyses that span local and global connectivity patterns highlighted.

Fig. 3 3D Potential of mean force of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{OH}$ solvated system along $r(\text{Na-OH})$ coordinate projected onto the Na atom PR distribution space. The projected 2D (r -PR) free energy surface map showing minima corresponding to CIP and SSIP Na-OH species is presented. Reprinted with permission from: Zhou, T.; Martinez-Baez, E.; Schenter, G.; Clark, A. E. PageRank as a collective variable to study complex chemical transformations and their energy landscapes. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 150, 134102, 2019. Copyright 2019 AIP Publishing.⁴⁹

sured using the geodesic index⁹⁷ and the closely related betweenness centrality,⁹⁸ both of which measure the normalized number of geodesic paths that a node in the network participates within (though the latter emphasizes the importance of a node to the geodesics). This metric has been very useful not only in the characterization of intermolecular networks, as employed to study the hydrogen bond networks of water-alcohol solutions above (and others), but also to understand macroscopic properties of complex solutions. For example, correlating relationships have

been shown between rheological properties of non-Newtonian colloidal suspensions and the global topology of networks of the forces between particles (specifically contact forces).⁹⁹ In that work, the geodesic index was used in tandem with another metric, called void analysis, that allowed simultaneous measurement of the interconnectedness of the contact force networks and regions that were absent of such interactions as a function of applied shear stress that induced a viscosity phase change. This approach revealed the shear thickening viscosity phase change's concomitant homogeneous growth of the force network across the entire system that systematically overcame local regions devoid of contacts.

Interconnectedness within a chemical network is also closely related to clustering and community analysis, which can presage a number of interesting phenomena in complex solutions. From the perspective of a chemist, one may consider cluster identification as a direct analogue to recognizing aggregation in a complex solution.^{7,44} Perhaps the simplest approach for this purpose is to consider the topology of a specific type of chemical interaction network in relation to the network of all interactions. An example of this is ion-ion clustering within a layered network of an electrolyte solution which consists of water-water, water-ion, and ion-ion interactions. The graph of these chemical networks can be partitioned into "clusters" or "communities." Clusters are defined by sets of nodes which are not connected to any node in another cluster through any path. That is, each cluster is a different connected component. Alternatively, a graph can be partitioned into communities, which defines sets of nodes having dense internal connectivity and sparse connectivity to other communities. This could include a dense set of connections between ions that exclude ion-water interactions in a concentrated electrolyte. There exist many different community identification algorithms, includ-

ing modularity optimization.¹⁰⁰ That method has been applied to identify communities within complex chemical networks of solutions. For example, we apply one such approach to quantify hierarchical structure in metal-ligand complex aggregation (as described in Sect. 5.2).⁴⁴ By partitioning the large aggregates (defined as clusters) which form at high concentration into communities, the composition of those clusters can be understood as a single network composed of loosely and densely interconnected subclusters. In summary, combinations of layered networks and methods of partitioning those layers can elucidate hierarchical structure in complex solutions.

3.3 Understanding 3D structure using persistent homology

Computational homology is an approach that derives from algebraic topology and measures how objects in space are connected. With respect to chemistry, the 3D space of molecules or assemblages therein, is modeled as a combinatorial object called the simplicial complex, which is a collection of vertices, edges, triangles, and higher order simplices glued together “nicely.”¹⁰¹ This creates an object that can be very similar to the voronoi cells described above, however the aim is to understand the connectivity of these simplicial complexes. Different ranks, or degrees of freedom, of the connectivity are measured via the “Betti numbers” and are denoted by β_i in dimension i . In chemical applications, the most intuitive ranks are of low dimension, where the β_0 counts the number of connected components in the object or space, β_1 counts the number of loops or holes, and β_2 counts the number of enclosed voids. Persistent homology¹⁰² produces a more comprehensive picture than simple homology of the shape of space by constructing a sequence of growing simplicial complexes, rather than a single complex. Changes in β_i values are tracked across this sequence, and this information is presented in a compact form as a “barcode” (one barcode in each dimension i). Although this approach has a long history in studying the 3D shapes of objects, it has begun to be applied to chemical systems, for example to understand protein structure and flexibility,¹⁰³ and more recently complex solutions.¹⁰⁴ Comparisons of NaCl and KSCN near the solubility limit have been shown to have very different layered network behavior, with compact ion clusters formed in the former and intertwined ion-ion and ion-water networks formed in the latter. Barcode analysis using persistent homology illustrated changes to the spatial extent of clusters commensurate with the traditional network analysis.

3.4 Subensemble Analysis and Lessons Learned From Predictive Spectroscopy

Subensemble analysis is a suite of methods that determine the contributions from specific chemical species of interest to the measured quantity of the complete ensemble. Effectively, this means collapsing a vast configurational space to a tractable number of states by combining metrics that may include cartesian position and intermolecular interaction topology. Though typical spatial or temporal correlation functions, like radial distribution functions, are incredibly useful for understanding average structural organization, they “hide” valuable information about struc-

Scheme 1

ture or correlations which may contribute significantly and differently to the macroscopic property of interest. Thus, subensemble methods can relate the spectroscopic signatures of specific chemical species to macroscopically obtained spectra (Scheme 1).

The identification of molecular species in complex solutions can be hindered by similarities in experimentally measured spectroscopic signatures. Combining theoretically derived spectroscopic signals and experimentally measured spectra has proven fundamental towards speciation elucidation in many instances.^{105,106} Notwithstanding, when a solution contains species with similar structural motifs, unambiguous signal assignments becomes challenging with either experimental or theoretical techniques. In these cases, molecular simulations are generally used to explore the speciation landscape and decipher signal overlapping between closely related species. An illustrative example pertains to the IR/Raman signals of highly alkaline Al^{3+} solutions.¹⁰⁵ Pouvreau et al.’s study utilized AIMD simulations to investigate the energetics and vibrational spectroscopic signatures of aqueous $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ and the dimers $\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_8^{2-}$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}(\text{OH})_6^{2-}$, employing comparisons with the $\text{K}_2[\text{Al}_2\text{O}(\text{OH})_6]$ crystal and experimental solution-phase spectra. The detailed analysis of the predicted Raman spectrum of $\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_8^{2-}$ (accounting for solvent fluctuations and anharmonicity) displayed a band at 608 cm^{-1} that was in direct overlap with the band of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ at 623 cm^{-1} . The overlapping bands derived from both $\mu(\text{Al}-\mu\text{O})_2$ and $\mu(\text{Al}-\text{O})$, and both associated structural features will also be present in higher order oligomers (Figure 4). This work indicated that the correlated contributions to the vibrational spectroscopy causes intrinsic uncertainty in the obtained speciation and thus limits the application for understanding nucleation and crystallization processes involving those species.

NMR techniques have been extensively used to determine the structure and characteristic of the chemical environments surrounding NMR active nuclei.^{107–109} NMR signals from liquid phase systems are generally a result of the average contribution of different rapidly inter-converting molecular environments.

Fig. 4 Experimental Raman spectra of a potassium aluminate solution in the 450-800 cm^{-1} range (black line), AIMD Raman main signatures of Al monomer and dimer species (in colors). Reprinted with permission from: Pouvreau, M.; Dembowski, M.; Clark, S. B.; Reynolds, J. G.; Rosso, K. M.; Schenter, G. K.; Pearce, C. I.; Clark, A. E.; Ab Initio Molecular Dynamics Reveal Spectroscopic Siblings and Ion Pairing as New Challenges for Elucidating Prenucleation Aluminum Speciation, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 122, 7394, 2018. Copyright 2018. American Chemical Society.¹⁰⁵

Theoretical calculations of NMR properties like shieldings (σ) or coupling constants, need to account for this ensemble averaging by some sampling technique (i.e., MD or Monte Carlo methods). Fig 5 shows the differences in the spread of the shielding distributions of two Al^{3+} species (octahedral $\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ and tetrahedral $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$) extracted from shielding tensor calculations of a MD ensemble of structures.¹¹⁰ Convergence of the Al average shielding of the two Al species was reached by sub-ensemble analysis of MD trajectories. Results showed the relative importance of different structural conformations to the average shielding. More importantly, this procedure allowed Martinez-Baez et al.¹¹⁰ to estimate solvation corrections to the absolute σ of both ^{27}Al species, calculated as the sum of solvent-screening (δ_{ss}) and solvent-induced dynamic effects (δ_{therm}). These were system-dependent both qualitatively (i.e., positive corrections in $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ vs negative in $\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$) and quantitatively very different (solvation error estimates were +3.7 and -9 ppm for $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ and $\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ respectively). Solvent-related effects were reckoned as the largest correction in ^{27}Al chemical shift computations of aluminate. In another instance, ^{27}Al NMR sensitivity to short and mid-range to long-range counter-ion pairing effects in $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ was studied through MD structural sampling.¹¹¹ The shielding constant of ^{27}Al was significantly affected only by short range Na^+ ion pairing electrostatic contributions below an ion-ion distance of 3 Å. Complementary Al K-edge X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) experiment and simulation of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ - NaOH electrolyte solutions identified a shift in the pre-edge shoulder correlated to sodium concentration.¹¹² In contrast to the NMR

that was less sensitive to long-range interactions, the physical origin of the XANES shift was attributed to longer-range ion interactions. The latter examples demonstrate the need for multimodal spectroscopic techniques to sample the breadth of species present in an ensemble.

Summary

The analysis of solution structure and speciation requires a large toolkit of algorithms and where necessary, understanding the uniqueness of different observables (uncertainty quantification). There have been significant advances to the breadth of algorithms available and continued emphasis upon tools that seamlessly characterize local and global behavior. This active area of research has also supported tighter integration of simulation and experiment to provide a deeper understanding of how the ensemble of local and non-local configurations influence experimental observation, reactivity, and macroscopic properties.

Fig. 5 Ensemble analysis of ^{27}Al shielding constants in $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ (red) and $\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ (blue) from AIMD simulations. Top and right panels are representing the kernel density estimation (KDE) –using a gaussian kernel– of isotropic and anisotropic shielding distributions respectively. Center panel shows the bivariate KDE heat maps of both Al species. Annotated colored dots on the center panel represent the shielding of $\text{Al}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ (blue) and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ (red) clusters optimized in vacuum employing the same computational method used for the AIMD run. Reprinted under the creative commons licence from: Martinez-Baez, E.; Feng, R.; Pearce, C. I.; Schenter, G. K.; Clark, A. E., ^{27}Al NMR chemical shift of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$ from first principles. Assessment of error cancellation in NMR chemical shift computations in chemically distinct reference and targeted systems. 2019, arXiv:2001.00107v1.¹¹⁰

4 Examples of Hierarchical Phenomena in Complex Solutions

4.1 Speciation, Organization, and Dynamics in the Bulk

Amongst the many features of complex solutions, is that the ensemble of local environments has the potential to be broad, where there is correlation between the local structure and extended organizational features, and where the dynamic properties can also be tightly coupled. The sampling methods employed, nature of the force field and associated benchmarking, and types of subensemble analyses, can dramatically impact fundamental interpretations of chemical outcomes and transformations. We present here a few examples that highlight these features and point to the specific combinations of simulation and experimental methods and analyses that elucidated them.

Example 1: Saturated Aqueous Electrolytes. At the infinite dilute limit, the structure and organization of solvation about aqueous ions is readily discovered using a number of methods, including PageRank.^{89,96} Understanding the changes to both water structure, and ion interactions as a function of ionic strength is surprisingly challenging both experimentally and computationally, and the current state of the knowledge is remarkably complicated. Although many aqueous electrolytes behave quite differently, we can illustrate a few key characteristics to consider and further, show how complex correlations and multi-timescale features emerge. Moving beyond the infinite dilute limit, one expects the the growth of solvent-separated and contact ion pair interactions (SSIP and CIP, respectively). As the saturation limit is approached, the system may follow a classical nucleation theory paradigm—where SSIP, CIP and solvated ions dominate the ensemble distribution yet thermal fluctuations facilitate the formation of a small concentration of pre-nucleation species and then clusters that exceed the critical size necessary to overcome the energy barrier caused by solid/liquid surface tension, to lead to spontaneous growth and crystallization. Alternatively, a pre-nucleation cluster paradigm has been proposed for some saturated aqueous electrolytes wherein the concentration of oligomeric, pre-nucleation clusters predominates the ensemble distribution of species and can then either lead to individual clusters that crystallize, or invoke an assembly or aggregation process for crystallization. Controversy over which nucleation process occurs has emerged for saturated $\text{CaCO}_3(\text{aq})$. Recent work¹¹³ combined advanced sampling (using aggregation-volume-bias Monte Carlo),¹¹⁴ complex interaction potentials derived from electronic structure theory, and potential of mean force methods, to create a self-consistent understanding that encompasses not only the ensemble distribution of all species in supersaturated conditions, but also the changes to free energy as a function of cluster size. This allowed the the predicted behavior of different experimental measurements could be obtained (e.g., titration curves that reflect the equilibrium between different species).

The crystallization process of CaCO_3 is in part a challenge to elucidate due to its low solubility in water which limits the suite of applicable experimental measurements. In contrast, systems that have very high aqueous solubility, for example NaOH, have significantly larger degrees of configurational freedom and thus have

different obstacles for understanding speciation ensembles and deriving mechanistic insight. Aqueous sodium hydroxide forms large extended networks of complex ion-ion interactions at increased concentrations. Near the solubility limit, a variety of local coordination environments are observed about Na^+ and OH^- . There are insufficient waters of solvation, and thus both ions and water participate in the local coordination environments about reference ions. The individual geometries present are polyhedral in shape, but the network of interconnected, face- and edges sharing polyhedral coordination environments is highly interconnected and can span large length-scales of the simulation box.^{7,115} Although overlapping atom-atom correlations hinders use of X-ray or neutron pair-distribution functions to uniquely determine speciation, subensemble analysis has been shown to provide insight into changes in peak intensities with varying concentrations of local environments. The extended ion networks found in saturated $\text{NaOH}(\text{aq})$ are further believed to be a contributing factor to unique multiple time-scale dynamic motion both OH^- and H_2O , as measured by quasi-elastic neutron scattering (QENS) and proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR).⁴ Although no short-time translational diffusion was observed at 293 K, several different localized motions were observed in the picosecond (ps) to microsecond (μs) timescale. These included “local backbone tumbling” of large hydrated ion clusters on the order of 40-60 ps; and “slower, complex, and collective dynamics” of all H-bearing species between 350-750 ps.

Example 2: Miscible Multi-Solvent Mixtures. Mixtures of solvents, such as short chain alcohols and water, are known to exhibit microheterogeneity: fluctuations in local structure and composition in the mixture beyond simple fluctuations observed in bulk phases of the individual components. These fluctuations can be detected experimentally with, e.g., scattering techniques. However, the diverse local environments are averaged in experimental measurements, complicating assignment of scattering features. As a result, molecular simulation has emerged as an essential technique for studying microheterogeneity in complex liquids. In this section we discuss simulation efforts to understand water/alcohol solvent mixtures, followed by more complex ternary solutions and finally ion solvation in binary solvent mixtures.

Methanol and water are miscible at all ratios of the cosolvents, however, their solution morphology changes as a function of volume fraction. While the local structure of methanol/water solutions are driven by familiar hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic (methyl-methyl) interactions, the resulting structure at different solvent ratios impact thermodynamic and kinetic properties of the bulk solution. Ethanol/water mixtures are of interest due to the incompatibility of the geometric structure of the three dimensional hydrogen bonded networks formed in pure water or pure ethanol. At low methanol fractions, small methanol clusters are isolated within the three dimensional water hydrogen bonded network. Conversely, at large methanol fractions, larger methanol hydrogen bonded chains form in solution.¹¹⁶ The preference of each cosolvent, when serving as the minor component, to form ring-like structures in solution result in inhomogeneity at larger length scales than their molecular sizes.¹¹⁶ Beginning at a methanol mole fraction of 0.27, the methanol minor component

becomes percolated simultaneously with the percolated water hydrogen bonding network.¹¹⁷ As a result of this co-percolation mole fraction, many transport and thermodynamic properties are near their maximum or minimum values.¹¹⁷

The microheterogeneity of water/alcohol mixtures has been described as smaller-scale analogs of microemulsions, including micelles and lamella.^{118–122} While the structure of true microemulsions, existing over 10s of nm to μm length scales, are not directly comparable to the microheterogeneity of these liquid mixtures, that description can explain the observed structural heterogeneity which extends beyond the normal fluctuations found in simple liquids. The impact of microheterogeneity on solution structure as observed in scattering profiles can, to some extent, be understood using the framework of well-studied microemulsion chemistry to describe the hierarchical solution structure.¹¹⁸

Nanoscale structures in ternary (water, short chain alcohol, long chain alcohol) mixtures have been characterized as surfactant-free microemulsions.¹²³ Combining small angle X-ray scattering and molecular dynamics simulation, the aggregation of the alcohols in the ternary mixture was characterized for certain volume fractions of the three components. In one case, near the octanol solubility limit in an ethanol/water mixture, octanol forms aggregates in analogy to oil-in-water micelles. The surface of these aggregates were found within ethanol-rich regions, coating the largely nonpolar octanol phase from the more polar water-rich domains of the solution¹²⁴ These studies help illustrate the rich chemistry of complex liquids with complex microheterogeneity manifested over nanometer length scales.

Complex solvent mixtures also impact solvation structure and dynamics of ions. Despite the importance of ion solvation, it is poorly understood in systems with multiple solvents. Properties of the ions, including activity and ligand exchange rates, are impacted by solvation. Therefore, a fundamental description of the impact of a mixed solvent on ion solvation and ion-ion interactions is important for understanding ion behavior in complex solutions. Kelley et al. studied the impact of combined methanol/water solvent on the solvation structure and dynamics of Na^+ and Cl^- ions¹²⁵ as well as the heavy actinide curium (Cm^{3+}).^{126,127} For Na^+ and Cl^- , potential of mean force simulations were conducted to study changes to first and second solvation shells along an ion pairing reaction coordinate.¹²⁵ They found solvation dynamics were significantly affected upon interaction of the ions' solvation shells. Conversely, ion-solvent distances were preserved upon formation of solvent-separated ion pairs, remaining unchanged until the formation of a contact ion pair. Ion pair formation was promoted by increased methanol content in the solvent, which was attributed to changing dielectric of solvent medium. Unlike Na^+ , ab initio molecular dynamics of solvated Cm^{3+} clusters revealed a larger dissociation energy for methanol than water, while the dissociation energy of both water and methanol were affected by the solvation composition.¹²⁶ Despite being more energetically favorable, the replacement of one water by methanol in the Cm^{3+} solvation shell substantially increased the kinetics of water dissociation from the solvation shell.¹²⁷ This finding highlights the complexity of reaction pathways introduced by the addition of additional species to

otherwise well-studied systems.

4.2 Phase Phenomena

Complex, multi-component solutions can exhibit similarly complex liquid/liquid phase transitions. Such phase transitions can be formidable to simulate directly due to time and length scale limitations. In particular, solutions that contain structures governed by a mixture of strong (e.g., ion-ion) and weak (e.g., van der Waals) interactions, simulations of chemical equilibria can be challenging. Grand canonical or Gibbs ensemble methods, where particles are exchanged between bulk phases such that those phases are in equilibrium, are difficult to implement for particles (or strongly bound species) that are large relative to cavities which form in the bulk phases. Persistent, metastable species that include a given particle can prevent ergodic sampling upon insertion of on such particle. Direct simulation of a liquid/liquid phase transition is similarly challenging. Kinetic barriers associated with phase splitting can be impossible to overcome for simulation-accessible time scales. Enhanced sampling of a collective phenomenon such as phase separation is not amenable to traditional free energy methods. Furthermore, were it possible to directly simulate the phase transition in a single simulation unit cell, the artificially high ratio of surface to bulk particles due to finite size effects could skew the predicted phase boundary. For real, macroscopic phases, a negligible fraction of all particles in a phase occupy the interface with another phase. However, in simulation, due to the finite size of the periodic system, that fraction is large (and dependent on unit cell geometry). Therefore, simulations have an artificially high contribution from the thermodynamically unfavorable interface, likely skewing the conditions under which phase separation is observed. As such, there is practical interest in identifying the onset of phase transitions in complex solutions without needing to directly simulate the phase transition itself.

Such an approach to observing a liquid-liquid phase transition in simulation using percolation theory is described by Oleinikova and coworkers.^{128,129} They found, for mixtures of water and tetrahydrofuran (THF), that the liquid-liquid phase boundary of the temperature-mole ratio phase diagram coincides approximately with the point at which both solvents form percolated networks in solution.¹²⁸ While percolation is a second order phase transition which occurs at the critical point and at the first order liquid-liquid phase transition which occurs below the critical temperature, the approximate co-location of the co-percolation boundary and the spinodal mean the percolation transition—readily observed from simulation—can demarcate the phase boundary. Care is taken to differentiate mesoscale fluctuations found in simulation, stabilized by the finite system size and sensitive to simulation unit size size, from critical fluctuations at the 3-dimension percolation threshold.¹²⁹

The percolation threshold can be identified in simulation by observing critical behavior of different structural properties which diverge at the percolation threshold. While formation of a truly infinite cluster is not possible in finite systems, the mesoscale behavior of certain properties are sensitive to the transition and can

indicate when the system is at the percolation threshold. The fractal dimension of the “infinite” cluster at the percolation threshold has a value of $d_f=2.5$ for three dimensions.¹²⁸ Similarly, the mean cluster size diverges at the percolation threshold, and the cluster size distribution follows the power law relationship $n_s = s^{-\tau}$, where the frequency of clusters of size s , n_s , is determined by the Fisher exponent, τ , whose value is approximately 2.19 in three dimensions. Clustering is particularly sensitive to the percolation threshold, and simple to determine from simulation trajectories, so it is a common property used to identify the percolation threshold. However, it is sensitive to the definition of connectivity, which is not uniquely defined for off-lattice simulations. Therefore, appropriate geometric or energetic definitions of connectivity need to be determined to describe connectivity. For this reason, combining clustering with a property which is not sensitive to the choice of connectivity, such as divergence of the correlation length or power law behavior of the fractal dimension, is a useful approach.

4.3 Liquid/Liquid Interfacial Phenomena

The interface of two immiscible liquids is a unique environment, not only because of the general decrease in degrees of freedom of the solvent and solute molecules, but also due to the fluctuational competition between solvent, co-solvent and solutes. The coupled local, thermal roughness of the surface, to the extended capillary wave characteristics of the interface, combined with interfacial permeability, distinguish virtually all aspects of liquid/liquid interfacial chemistry from solid/liquid interfacial chemistry. Although significant research has been performed upon the average perturbations to solvent interactions over 1-2 nm regions of the interface.^{130–135} interest in the properties of the instantaneous surface is growing within the literature. In recent years, the importance of the instantaneous surface has gained attention, as it is this very specific region deemed responsible for interfacial reactivity and transport processes. As the subensemble and topological analyses methods described above have become more advanced, and as simulation capabilities have increased, a more holistic understanding of the structure, property, and reactivity, of the interface is slowly developing. In this vein we present examples that support a growing consensus that the liquid/liquid interface can have tailored properties via the systematic modulation of the ensemble of local environments.

Interfacial Heterogeneity at the Molecular Level. As demonstrated in several studies,^{136–138} the local structure of the instantaneous surface is highly heterogeneous, both structurally and dynamically. By combining traditional “slab” layering analysis of the interfacial structure, with the properties of the instantaneous surface (identified using the “Identification of Truly Interfacial Molecules” algorithm)^{137,139} it is possible to differentiate between the properties of capillary-wave crests and troughs.¹³⁶ In the case of aqueous interfaces with vapor or non-polar media, crest regions (which protrude into the opposing phase) have similar characteristics of dangling H-bonds and molecular orientations of water that align the molecular dipole perpendicular to the interface normal.^{136,137} In contrast, troughs (which

protrude into the aqueous phase) exhibit HB characteristics similar to the bulk. As one might anticipate, the presence of surfactants introduces new competitive interactions that can significantly alter interfacial heterogeneity. In the case of tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP), surfactant adsorption increases heterogeneity due to strong HB interactions of TBP and H₂O that causes formation of water bridged TBP dimers under surface monolayer conditions.¹⁴⁰

The heterogeneous characteristics of the interface further extend to the local solvation environments of solutes that reside therein. The molecular scale behavior of small ions in the interfacial region has been significantly studied, however remains controversial with respect to their effect upon capillary wave structure. This topic has gained significant attention within the last decade, where earlier work indicated that ions at the interface “pin” capillary waves and decrease the interfacial area of the surface,^{141,142} whereas more recent work has surmised that the original conclusion derived from finite size effects of the interfacial area and that in fact interfacial ions enhances capillary wave fluctuations.¹⁴³ Study of heavier ions (or ionic complexes) indicates that their solvation behavior at the interface can be quite different than lighter ions that follow expectations from the Hofmeister series (which informs the change in solvation free energy from the loss of H₂O of solvation at the interface). In one instance, PtCl₆²⁻ have been shown to adsorb at positively charged interfaces in a two-step process.³⁵ A combination of vibrational sum frequency generation and molecular dynamics with subensemble analysis revealed that this interesting adsorption behavior may be related to well-defined changes to solvation environment. After adsorption PtCl₆²⁻ complexes were demonstrated to partially retain their first and second hydration spheres, such that three different types of water molecules around could be identified based upon their orientational structures and hydrogen-bonding strengths.

Interfacial Heterogeneity and Transport. The coupled nature of interfacial heterogeneity and permeability toward solute transport is a growing area of research and at the forefront of potential design principles that leverage this behavior to optimize transport kinetics in a number of applications domains, including solvent extraction. Early work of ion and metal-ligand complex transport focused upon non-equilibrium observations of transport processes,^{144–146} and under equilibrium conditions employed potential of mean force methods, and free energy methods (Section 2.4), to understand transport energetics. Yet it is apparent that distance-based collective coordinates for PMF simulations are rife with difficulty, not the least of which is that the heterogeneous nature of the surface implies that many PMF’s must be performed to sample the dependency of the transport energetics upon the local characteristics of the instantaneous surface.

In the case of ion transport, the importance of interfacial roughness upon the mechanism and energetics was initially observed nearly 30 years ago, and included the observation of water fingers or protrusions that may be considered amplifications of the crest of the surface into a new structural motif.¹⁴⁷ The fundamental timescales of the fluctuations in the surface roughness, the equilibrium behavior of the water protrusions (i.e., not all protrusions should be successful in transport and may become re-adsorbed

into the instantaneous surface), complicate study and necessitate extensive sampling in order to have statistical relevance. More recent work^{65,66} has proposed a collective variable for ion transport derived from connectivity between the ion-solvating water finger and the water intersurface (see Figure 6). The so-called water finger coordinate is the minimum distance required for connectivity between water molecules to connect, through any path, the ion to the water interface. This CV (the distance needed to connect the ion protruding into the organic phase and the bulk water phase) satisfied several criterion, including its ability to account for the local instantaneous surface configuration, however it was not examined from the perspective of committer probabilities, as described in Sect. 2.4. The free energy landscape for ion transport within this CV framework, indicated a “hidden barrier” for ion transport (meaning two separated minima along the coordinate) associated with different configurational ensembles of water protrusion formation and breakage. Benjamin and coworkers have compared these reaction coordinates and studied them for a variety of liquid/liquid interfaces and ions.^{148–150}

The role of protrusions as a broader mechanism for solute transport, and the ability to modulate protrusion formation, has recently begun to be explored. Servis et al. found that the ability of surfactants like TBP to amplify interfacial heterogeneity also facilitated formation of water protrusions and were the dominant mechanism by which water was transferred from the aqueous to organic phase. As indicated by Figure 6, the distribution of the configurational ensemble associated with water protrusion is significantly larger in the presence of surfactants, and there exist many metastable configurations of surfactant-water aggregates within the organic side of the instantaneous surface that evolve to form the water-bridged TBP dimer that is observed in the bulk organic solvent. Further, it has been our unpublished observation that the equilibrium distribution of protrusions indicates correlations in morphology and composition with the likelihood of success for water transport across the interface.

5 Solvent Extraction: The Confluence of Complex Solutions, Interfacial Chemistry, and Coupled Behavior

Solvent extraction is the most widely used industrial technique for purification and separations of complex multicomponent solutions into their constituents.^{151–153} The separation driving force derives from the differential solubilities of the solutes between two different immiscible liquids, usually water and an organic solvent (Figure 7). The chemistry in solvent extraction draws from many concepts related to complex solutions, including broad distributions of speciation and local environments in a bulk aqueous phase, liquid/liquid interfacial chemistry and transport therein, and the potential for hierarchical organization in the organic phase that can lead to new phase phenomena. Although solvent extraction is a very old technology, many important changes have occurred within the field that are transforming the research landscape and reinventing historical paradigms. For example, interfacial characterization is beginning to be performed under conditions that approach industrial relevance,^{35,154} and multi-

Fig. 6 (A) Time sequence of protrusion formation from the instantaneous surface to enable ion transport. Adapted with permission from: Kikkawa, N.; Wang, L.; Morita, Microscopic barrier mechanism of ion transport through liquid–liquid interface. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 137, 8022, 2015. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. (B) Time sequence of protrusion formation from the TBP-laden instantaneous surface to support water transport. Adapted with permission from: Servis, M. J.; Clark, A. E. Surfactant-enhanced heterogeneity of the aqueous interface drives water extraction into organic solvents. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 21, 2866, 2019. Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry.¹⁴⁰

modal measurements¹⁵⁴ and in situ capabilities (notably using scattering methods) are creating ever-more detailed understanding of complex solution structure.¹⁵⁵ Many, but not all, of these considerations also apply to chromatographic separations.^{156–158} Within this section, we illustrate how the molecular-perspective of hierarchical phenomena of the complex solutions (Section 4), including the simulation and analyses described in Sections 2 and 3, is helping to advance the science of solvent extraction to create more efficient and selective separations, as noted by the recently released National Academy of Sciences Committee consensus study on a Research Agenda for Transforming Separations Science.¹⁵⁹

5.1 The Aqueous Phase

Here we focus upon solvent extraction of metal-containing acidic aqueous solutions. Industrial sources may derive from ore purification, recycling, remediation of contaminated environmental sites, and metal processing. Perhaps one of the worst-case scenarios regarding composition complexity are the aqueous solutions that derive from dissolution of spent nuclear fuel during energy production. After fission and irradiation in a nuclear reactor, nuclear fuels contain isotopes of most elements on the periodic table.¹⁶⁰ This diversity of nuclide constituents represents a substantial separations problem. This challenge is especially pronounced in the separation of actinides (An) and lanthanides (Ln), which

Fig. 7 Three primary solution environments in liquid/liquid extraction: the aqueous phase (right), the organic phase (left) and their interface (center). Different challenges exist in studying each environment. In the aqueous phase, solvent-ion dynamics depend strongly on the metal ion's first solvation shell upon introduction of a cosolvent.¹²⁶ At the interface, surface-active extractants interact with surface water across a heterogeneous surface.¹⁴⁰ In the organic phase, a broad range of energetic and association length scales introduce hierarchical organization.⁴⁴

often feature similar chemistry but dramatically different half-lives and radioactivities. Partitioning An and Ln is essential for limiting volumes of the longest-lived radionuclides which require long-term storage in geologic repositories. For example, removal of An from fuel, coupled with transmutation, can reduce the time until radioactivity is reduced two orders of magnitude from 130,000 years to 500 years.¹⁶¹ Despite the known complexity of varying concentrations of An and Ln, their nuanced differences in electronic structure, and the high concentrations of potentially complexing acid anions like nitrate and chloride, most work on understanding An and Ln speciation has been performed near the infinite dilute limit. Indeed, much work has focused solely upon understanding aqueous solvation of these ions, accurately predicting their solvation free energies, and dynamic properties like the exchange rates with water that serve as an upper bound to complexation rates in dissociative mechanisms.^{94,95} Such fundamental properties have historically been challenging, as dramatically different solvation and coordination environments occur depending on the oxidation state (which is controlled by pH), wherein tri- and tetravalent ions are atomic and with varying solvation numbers from 8-9, whereas the penta- and hexavalent An exist as linear dioxo $\text{AnO}_2^{1+/2+}$ actinyl ions. Significant polarization effects are observed across solvation shells for the 3+/4+ cations and there has been much controversy in the literature regarding the necessity of polarizable force fields within classical simulations even in the infinite dilution limit (see Section 2.1).

Recognizing the complexity of An and Ln solutions in nuclear fuel reprocessing, early work to identify the ensemble distribution of solvated, ion-paired, solvent-separated ion-paired, etc. species, focused upon gas-phase stability calculations, hydrated clusters in the gas-phase, and mixed cluster/continuum representations of the extended solvation environment about different local configurations.^{94,95} In general the lack of reliable force fields for such

complex aqueous solutions has necessitated more recent work to employ AIMD methods using enhanced sampling to attempt to understand the ensemble environment solely at a local level. For example, the impact of non-complexing background electrolyte interactions has begun to be studied. For both Cm^{3+} and Th^{4+} ions, the presence of counterions not in the first solvation shell can perturb first solvation shell dynamic behavior.^{162,163} AIMD combined with HB lifetime analysis and the energetics of solvent exchange indicate that counterions like perchlorate can stabilize or strengthen the Th^{4+} hydration shell.¹⁶³ Other, direct, ion-pairing phenomena have begun to be studied, and amongst the most chemically interesting are those involving cations with other cations. So-called "cation-cation" complexes have been observed under a number of high ionic strength solutions related to nuclear fuel reprocessing (e.g., post Plutonium Uranium Reduction Extraction).¹⁶⁴ Actinyl-actinyl complexes,¹⁶⁵ as well as actinyl- M^{x+} ¹⁶⁶ can form and have interesting bonding interactions that involve partial charge-transfer between occupied and empty orbitals that stabilize formation.¹⁶⁷

The significant historical effort, both experimentally and computationally, has led to much insight into local An and Ln interactions within aqueous electrolytes. This knowledge has been leveraged within the design of extracting ligands that are selective to specific ions because they either take advantage of different preferred coordination environments about these ions, or specific orbital interactions. There is thus an enthalpic driving force for complexation of An or Ln ions when they approach the interfacial region and encounter the surface active extracting ligand. Under idealized conditions the ensemble distribution of all aqueous species of the An and Ln ions (whether they be different solvation environments or complexed by acid anions) does not significantly alter the thermodynamic favorability of the extractant complexation. However, as will be discussed below, industrial conditions for solvent extraction are far from ideal limits and instead of traditional inorganic coordination chemistry, soft-matter self-assembly processes are beginning to be recognized as an influential part of the interfacial chemistry of ion transport. In this vein, it is entirely possible (based upon the observations from Section 4) that both the ensemble of all local environments, as well as longer-length scale correlations, influence speciation at the interface and the subsequent mechanisms of transport processes. As such, there is significant motivation and opportunity for more robust and systematic studies that utilize classical MD of higher ionic strength electrolytes of heavy elements solutions to investigate solution structure across lengthscales. Yet there are many hurdles that derive from the fundamental methodological challenges described in Sect. 2 and continued efforts need to be made to integrate the statistical mechanical understanding of such solutions as well as the electronic structure that can drive actinide ion interactions in the aqueous phase.

5.2 The Organic Phase

The molecular structure of the organic phase is essential to understanding the energetic drivers behind solvent extraction. The

distribution ratio, D , for solute A , defined as

$$D = \frac{[A]_{\text{org}}}{[A]_{\text{aq}}}, \quad (9)$$

where $[A]_{\text{org}}$ and $[A]_{\text{aq}}$ are the concentrations of that solute in the organic and aqueous phases, respectively. The distribution ratio of a any solute depends strongly on its organic phase speciation. For metal ions, the enthalpic favorability of metal-extractant coordination and subsequent change in solvation free energy is often the primary driver for extraction (where bulk organic solvation is favored). For this reason, organic phases have broadly been understood through coordination chemistry paradigms. This approach is applicable in the dilute limit where the populations and relative energetics of non-interacting coordination complexes can be modeled analytically. These models depend upon enumerating all relevant species—a task that is only practical in the low concentration limit. However, solvent extraction processes at low target metal concentrations generally occur in analytical applications; industrial applications operate far from that ideal limit.

Under high solute concentrations, analytical speciation models fail because the speciation ensemble becomes too broad to enumerate a priori (without knowledge from simulation), and the interactions between species becomes significant. The energetic drivers of solute distribution between phases is further affected by aggregation that occurs at non-ideal concentrations.^{168,169} As non-ideal solution conditions limit the accuracy of simplistic coordination complex-based separations design strategies, other modeling approaches have emerged. These techniques include analytical free energy models,^{170–172} inspired by the work of Osseo-Asare who proposed the organic phases behaves as a microemulsion,¹⁷³ and molecular simulation techniques that allow for aggregation of extractants and extracted solutes. Here, we discuss those recent simulation efforts to elucidate aggregation in solvent extraction organic phases.

Organic phase aggregation with neutral solvating extractants occurs through dipole-dipole association of the extractants^{174–177} as well as through various physical interactions including the extracted polar solutes extractant molecules. As these interactions are diverse in physical origin, ranging from ion-ion and ion-dipole interactions to hydrogen bonding, their impact is strongly system dependent. For example, in the absence of metal ions, PUREX-type organic phases (the organic phase of tri-*n*-butyl (TBP) in *n*-dodecane with a nitric acid-based aqueous phase) have been investigated. These studies have shown that the resulting speciation, driving by hydrogen bonding of the extractant with associated nitric acid and water, drives the speciation in the absence of clear micellization.^{3,178,179} Upon the inclusion of metal ions, it has also been suggested for certain solvent extraction systems that hydrogen bonding plays an important role in the organic phase structure, including in the coordination environment of those metal ions. Using a malonamide extractant, several studies using MD have found that metal ions are incorporated into extractant-water-acid hydrogen bonded networks.^{180–182} This implies a strong dependence of metal distribution energetics (beyond the metal-extractant binding) on the mesoscale order of the

organic phase induced by extractant-solute interactions. Conversely, that behavior of malonamide is contrasted with PUREX-type organic phases, where the TBP-metal interaction dominates. That interaction largely eliminates weaker solute-ion interactions in the first coordination sphere of the metal ion. However, other forms of TBP-metal complex association can still occur, as have been reported in the simulation literature for TBP complexes with UO_2 ^{6,183} and Zr .¹⁸⁴ In the case of uranyl nitrate extraction by TBP, the organic phase consists primarily of association $(\text{TBP})_2(\text{UO}_2)(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complexes.¹⁸⁵ The strong, local interactions dictate the geometry of the metal-ligand complexes which their weaker association over larger distances leads to hierarchical organization of the solution, as illustrated in Figure 8. The aggregation of associating $(\text{TBP})_2(\text{UO}_2)(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complexes, themselves composed of ion-ion and ion-dipole interactions, are quantified with graph theory by coarse graining each entire complex to a single node on a graph.⁴⁴ In combination with connectivity defined for local ion-ion, ion-dipole and hydrogen bonding interactions, the overall structure of the solution can be quantified at different length scales.

Fig. 8 Multi-component solutions with a broad range of interaction and length scales result in hierarchical organization. Here, $(\text{TBP})_2(\text{UO}_2)(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complexes are treated as single nodes in a graph to identify clustering, densely interconnected subclusters. Reprinted under the creative commons licence from Servis, M. J. and Wu, D. T. and Shafer, J. C. and Clark, A. Reimagining Third Phase Formation as the Miscibility Gap of a Molecular Solution, 2019, ChemRxiv DOI:10.26434/chemrxiv.10060253.v1

A quintessential phenomenon that results from organic phase aggregation is third phase formation. In third phase formation, after sufficient polar solute extraction into the nonpolar organic phase, that phase splits into “light” and “heavy” phases. The light organic phase consists mostly of the organic solvent while the heavy phase contains nearly all of the extractant and extracted solutes. This deleterious phenomenon is a processing impediment and to design solvent extraction systems which avoid third phase formation requires an understanding of organic phase aggregation. Third phase formation has been the subject of recent molecular simulation studies. In the absence of metal ions, Braley and coworkers found that the water and acid content in organic phase corresponded to the onset of third phase formation, and that this approximately coincides with the formation of a system-spanning hydrogen bonding network.³ Therefore, the approach discussed above in Sect. 4.2 concerning the application of percolation theory to understand liquid-liquid phase transitions appears to apply to third phase formation in this system. While the percolation

transition is an independent event from the thermodynamic phase boundary, their approximate co-location and the ability to identify percolation in simulation presents a means to relate molecular-scale interactions to the onset of third phase formation. For the same system, Mu et al. reported equilibrium between light and heavy phases using grand canonical MD simulations,¹⁷⁹ finding hydrogen bonded structures which were qualitatively consistent with those reported by Braley and coworkers.³

The suite of simulation and analyses methods described in Sections 2 and 3 are dramatically changing the understanding of organic phase speciation and phase phenomena. Although the traditional coordination-complex inspired design criterion for solvent extraction still provides significant relevance to selectivity, the complexity of both aqueous and organic phases is highly relevant to extraction efficiencies. In the organic phase, the industrially relevant solution conditions facilitate coupling of the local speciation with phase phenomena. As indicated above, there is growing evidence that by understanding both the speciation ensemble and the interactions across lengthscales, we are developing a predictive capability for the onset of third phase formation. Given the significant effort worldwide to expand the suite of organic diluent compositions and extracting ligand architectures for solvent extraction, a predictive understanding of organic phase speciation and phase transformations is becoming much more industrially relevant.

5.3 The Aqueous/Organic Interface

While the bulk aqueous and organic phases feature their own rich chemistry, the structure of the interface is perhaps even more complex, owing to the interaction between the polar and non-polar species and the structural asymmetry inherent to interfaces. The interface plays an important role in solvent extraction processes: the interface is where the extractant molecules complex with aqueous solutes. Therefore, the formation of those complexes and their disengagement from the interfacial region—processes which are not necessarily independent—are kinetically relevant. Broadly, these two steps have been the focus of research on interfacial kinetics in solvent extraction.

Due to the nature of the nonpolar organic phase, extractant-polar solute complexes are charge neutral. Given that extractants generally have very low solubility in the aqueous phase, it is presumed that the charge neutral species are assembled at the interface. This assembly process, then, is the primary physical reaction which much occur before diffusion of the charge neutral complex from the interface to the bulk. Experimental studies, using techniques such as vibrational sum frequency generation, have attempted to observe changes to vibrational modes of interfacial water, anions¹⁸⁶ or the extractant head group.^{187,188} Vibrational changes to the latter would indicate the formation of strong metal-ligand interactions. However, due to the spatial and time averaged vibrational signal and the relatively small concentration of metal ions at the interface (and therefore contribution of metal-extractant interactions to the total signal), the detail of structural changes observed from these techniques is limited.

As a result of these experimental challenges, simulations have

strong potential to supplement our understanding of interfacial reactions.³⁵ A primary goal of simulation efforts has been to understand the extractant-solute complexation reactions which occur at the interface. Liang et al. combined X-ray surface scattering and MD simulation, proposing a complex bilayer structure at the interface, with ion transport occurring through a micelle budding mechanism.¹⁸⁹ Wipff and coworkers applied classical and ab initio molecular dynamics to study the energetics of numerous reaction pathways relevant to extractant/uranyl/anion complexation.^{190–192} Khomami and coworkers have also studied how TBP/uranyl nitrate complexes form at the interface and diffuse into the organic phase.^{193,194} Such simulation studies of uranyl transport are challenging because the coordination number (CN) of the uranyl metal center is different in aqueous versus organic phase environments: the equatorial plane of the uranyl dioxocation is 5-coordinate in the aqueous phase and 6-coordinate in the organic phase. Ye et al. concluded that the six-fold coordination observed experimentally for the extracted $(\text{TBP})_2\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ complex^{195,196} must form once the 5-coordinate complex diffuses from the interface.¹⁹⁴ The metastability of metal-ligand complexes, driven by strong intermolecular interactions, limits transitions between denticity in the absence of advanced sampling methods that require prescribed reaction coordinates. To further complicate simulation approaches, other studies have found that uranyl models, generally developed for five-coordinate solvation in aqueous environments, often remain five-coordinate in the organic phase.⁶ The coordination number is determined through the atom's nonbonded potentials and capturing transitions between CNs that result from changing solution conditions is not simple. Similarly, complicating the treatment of acidic molecules in both polar and nonpolar phases, classical MD force fields generally require prescribed protonation states: common molecular mechanical models cannot change protonation state during the course of a simulation. Therefore, the simulation of charge neutralizing anions that are simultaneously deprotonated acids, represents a significant obstacle because of the need to predict the appropriate protonation states in both aqueous and organic environments.

Simpler biphasic systems provide the opportunity to systematically investigate the importance of different molecular interactions, speciation, and ensemble behavior within an extraction process. For example, the mechanisms of extractant-solute interaction and disengagement from the interface have been studied in detail. While liquid/liquid interfaces naturally feature structural and dynamic heterogeneity across the rough surface,¹³⁶ the surface active nature of amphiphilic extractant molecules dramatically increases that heterogeneity. Therefore, study of interfaces under high surfactant concentrations requires coupling the molecules' occupation of the thermally corrugated interface from their position relative to the time averaged interfacial plane to account for molecular positions at capillary wave crests and troughs. Then, combining a graph theoretic description of, e.g., the extractant-water hydrogen bonded network with a method of identifying which molecules occupy the immediately interfacial layers,¹⁹⁷ detailed descriptions of extractant/polar molecule (e.g., water) interfacial disengagement mechanisms can be stud-

ied.¹⁴⁰ Interestingly, recent work is indicating that interfacial heterogeneity is highly tunable based upon the nature of the surfactant, a feature that impacts ion solvation and concentrations within the interfacial region. Although electrolyte/vapor interfaces are well-known, ions have been shown to reside selectively within “trough” regions of the capillary wave front of the instantaneous surface.¹⁹⁸ However, the analogous electrolyte/octanol interfaces exhibit significant interdigitation of water and octanol molecules that in turn decreases heterogeneity of the instantaneous surface. The surprising result of this is that there is a large increase in ion concentration in the electrolyte/octanol interfacial region not because octanol helps to solvate the ions, but rather because the strong water-octanol interactions decrease the ion’s tendency to lose waters of solvation.

The emerging molecular-scale understanding of the liquid/liquid interface - not only in terms of organization and dynamics, but also the competition of forces, is paving the way for a paradigm shift regarding the way in which these interfaces are employed for many different applications. In the context of solvent extraction, there are a number of exciting opportunities where liquid/liquid interfaces have the potential to be tailored to optimize specific mechanisms of transport and thus improve extraction efficiency. Necessarily, there is significant motivation for continued improvements to the simulation methods and analyses so as to systematically begin to increase interfacial complexity while accounting for the very real behavior of acid-base chemistry, changes to solute preferred environments, and larger-scale collective motions of the interface. These challenges stimulate both the theoretical and simulation communities and inspire new experimental measurements and solution conditions.

6 Conclusions

Multicomponent liquids represents a substantial opportunity for molecular simulation techniques to advance our understanding of fundamental chemistry, while also presenting unique challenges in the application of those computational methods. A primary computational challenge in multicomponent solutions is the effective sampling of the complex energy landscapes that is the result of diverse interactions having different length, time and energy scales. In this article, we discuss recent efforts toward developing and implementing interaction potentials for use in diverse solution conditions as well as technical challenges, including ergodic limitations and finite size effects. Analysis of simulation data from complex, multicomponent solutions also requires careful consideration, a topic of focus significant development within computational chemistry literature. Recent work has included order parameter development for complex condensed phase reactions, which are discussed in this article with an emphasis on techniques based on computational topology. While such graph theoretic and other analysis tools can be applied to many different chemical problems, we contextualize recent efforts from the perspective of complex bulk phase speciation, phase transitions and liquid/liquid interfaces. Finally, we discuss a specific scientific application that incorporates and integrates the topics featured throughout this article: solvent extraction. The combination of solution structure driven by complex, hierarchical interac-

tions, along with heterogeneous liquid/liquid interfaces and liquid/liquid phase transitions, make this an particularly insightful application. Recent simulation efforts aimed toward understanding solvent extraction have highlighted the challenges discussed throughout the article and have ultimately demonstrated the potential value of the fundamental chemistry of complex solutions and hierarchical phenomena therein.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

For technical content by the authors associated with the chemistry of concentrated electrolytes and integration of spectroscopic observables and subensemble analyses, the authors acknowledge the Interfacial Dynamics in Radioactive Environments and Materials (IDREAM), an Energy Frontier Research Center funded by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Basic Energy Sciences. PNNL is a multiprogram national laboratory operated for DOE by Battelle Memorial Institute under contract no. DE-AC05-76RL0-1830. For technical content by the authors regarding network analysis algorithm development, the chemistry of liquid/liquid interfaces, complex organic solutions and solvent extraction science, the authors acknowledge the Department of Energy, Basic Energy Sciences Separations program (DE-SC0001815).

Notes and references

- 1 K. J. Laidler and H. Gerischer, *The world of physical chemistry*, Oxford University Press Oxford, 1995, vol. 3.
- 2 C. H. Pham, S. K. Reddy, K. Chen, C. Knight and F. Paesani, Many-body interactions in ice, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2017, **13**, 1778–1784.
- 3 M. J. Servis, D. T. Wu and J. C. Braley, Network analysis and percolation transition in hydrogen bonded clusters: nitric acid and water extracted by tributyl phosphate, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2017, **19**, 11326–11339.
- 4 T. R. Graham, D. Semrouni, E. Mamontov, A. J. Ramirez-Cuesta, K. Page, A. Clark, G. K. Schenter, C. I. Pearce, A. G. Stack and H.-W. Wang, Coupled Multimodal Dynamics of Hydrogen-Containing Ion Networks in Water-Deficient, Sodium Hydroxide-Aluminate Solutions, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2018, **122**, 12097–12106.
- 5 B. Peters, Reaction coordinates and mechanistic hypothesis tests, *Annual review of physical chemistry*, 2016, **67**, 669–690.
- 6 M. J. Servis, D. T. Wu, J. C. Shafer and A. E. Clark, Square supramolecular assemblies of uranyl complexes in organic solvents, *Chemical Communications*, 2018, **1**, 10064–10067.
- 7 D. Semrouni, H.-W. Wang, S. B. Clark, C. I. Pearce, K. Page, G. Schenter, D. J. Wesolowski, A. G. Stack and A. E. Clark, Resolving local configurational contributions to X-ray and neutron radial distribution functions within solutions of concentrated electrolytes—a case study of concentrated NaOH, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2019, **21**, 6828–6838.

- 8 E. Wernersson and P. Jungwirth, Effect of water polarizability on the properties of solutions of polyvalent ions: Simulations of aqueous sodium sulfate with different force fields, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2010, **6**, 3233–3240.
- 9 I. Leontyev and A. Stuchebrukhov, Accounting for electronic polarization in non-polarizable force fields, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2011, **13**, 2613–2626.
- 10 E. Duboué-Dijon, P. E. Mason, H. E. Fischer and P. Jungwirth, Hydration and ion pairing in aqueous Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺ solutions: force-field description aided by neutron scattering experiments and ab initio molecular dynamics simulations, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2017, **122**, 3296–3306.
- 11 T. Martinek, E. Duboué-Dijon, Š. Timr, P. E. Mason, K. Baxová, H. E. Fischer, B. Schmidt, E. Pluhařová and P. Jungwirth, Calcium ions in aqueous solutions: Accurate force field description aided by ab initio molecular dynamics and neutron scattering, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2018, **148**, 222813.
- 12 A. Benavides, M. Portillo, V. Chamorro, J. Espinosa, J. Abascal and C. Vega, A potential model for sodium chloride solutions based on the TIP4P/2005 water model, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2017, **147**, 104501.
- 13 I. Zeron, J. Abascal and C. Vega, A force field of Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Cl⁻, and SO₄²⁻ in aqueous solution based on the TIP4P/2005 water model and scaled charges for the ions, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2019, **151**, 134504.
- 14 J. Wang, P. Cieplak and P. A. Kollman, How well does a restrained electrostatic potential (RESP) model perform in calculating conformational energies of organic and biological molecules?, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2000, **21**, 1049–1074.
- 15 T. Yan, C. J. Burnham, M. G. Del Pópolo and G. A. Voth, Molecular dynamics simulation of ionic liquids: The effect of electronic polarizability, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2004, **108**, 11877–11881.
- 16 Y. Yasaka, M. L. Klein, M. Nakahara and N. Matubayasi, Communication: Exploring the reorientation of benzene in an ionic liquid via molecular dynamics: Effect of temperature and solvent effective charge on the slow dynamics, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2011, **134**, 191101.
- 17 S. Cui, V. de Almeida, B. Hay, X. Ye and B. Khomami, Molecular dynamics simulation of tri-*n*-butyl-phosphate liquid: a force field comparative study., *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2012, **116**, 305–313.
- 18 J. W. Ponder, C. Wu, P. Ren, V. S. Pande, J. D. Chodera, M. J. Schnieders, I. Haque, D. L. Mobley, D. S. Lambrecht, R. A. DiStasio Jr *et al.*, Current status of the AMOEBA polarizable force field, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2010, **114**, 2549–2564.
- 19 L. Tůma, D. Jeníček and P. Jungwirth, Propensity of heavier halides for the water/vapor interface revisited using the Amoeba force field, *Chemical physics letters*, 2005, **411**, 70–74.
- 20 Y. Mao, O. Demerdash, M. Head-Gordon and T. Head-Gordon, Assessing ion–water interactions in the amoeba force field using energy decomposition analysis of electronic structure calculations, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2016, **12**, 5422–5437.
- 21 C. Zhang, C. Lu, Z. Jing, C. Wu, J.-P. Piquemal, J. W. Ponder and P. Ren, AMOEBA polarizable atomic multipole force field for nucleic acids, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2018, **14**, 2084–2108.
- 22 Y. Shi, Z. Xia, J. Zhang, R. Best, C. Wu, J. W. Ponder and P. Ren, Polarizable atomic multipole-based AMOEBA force field for proteins, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2013, **9**, 4046–4063.
- 23 Z. Jing, C. Liu, S. Y. Cheng, R. Qi, B. D. Walker, J.-P. Piquemal and P. Ren, Polarizable force fields for biomolecular simulations: Recent advances and applications, *Annual Review of biophysics*, 2019, **48**, 371–394.
- 24 F. Réal, V. Vallet, J.-P. Flament and M. Masella, Revisiting a many-body model for water based on a single polarizable site: From gas phase clusters to liquid and air/liquid water systems, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2013, **139**, 114502.
- 25 F. Réal, M. Trumm, V. Vallet, B. Schimmelpfennig, M. Masella and J.-P. Flament, Quantum chemical and molecular dynamics study of the coordination of Th (IV) in aqueous solvent, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2010, **114**, 15913–15924.
- 26 F. Réal, M. Trumm, B. Schimmelpfennig, M. Masella and V. Vallet, Further insights in the ability of classical nonadditive potentials to model actinide ion–water interactions, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2013, **34**, 707–719.
- 27 E. Acher, M. Masella, V. Vallet and F. Réal, Properties of the tetravalent actinide series in aqueous phase from a microscopic simulation automated engine, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2020, DOI: 10.1039/C9CP04912F.
- 28 F. Réal, V. Vallet and M. Masella, Improving the description of solvent pairwise interactions using local solute/solvent three-body functions. The case of halides and carboxylates in aqueous environment, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2019, **40**, 1209–1218.
- 29 D. Hagberg, G. Karlström, B. O. Roos and L. Gagliardi, The coordination of uranyl in water: a combined quantum chemical and molecular simulation study, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2005, **127**, 14250–14256.
- 30 D. Hagberg, E. Bednarz, N. M. Edelstein and L. Gagliardi, A quantum chemical and molecular dynamics study of the coordination of Cm (III) in water, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2007, **129**, 14136–14137.
- 31 P. Li and K. M. Merz Jr, Taking into account the ion-induced dipole interaction in the nonbonded model of ions, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2013, **10**, 289–297.
- 32 P. Li, L. F. Song and K. M. Merz Jr, Parameterization of highly charged metal ions using the 12-6-4 LJ-type nonbonded model in explicit water, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2014, **119**, 883–895.

- 33 P. Li, L. F. Song and K. M. Merz Jr, Systematic parameterization of monovalent ions employing the nonbonded model, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2015, **11**, 1645–1657.
- 34 M. J. Servis, A. McCue, A. J. Casella and A. E. Clark, The Role of Surfactant Force Field on the Properties of Liquid/Liquid Interfaces, *ChemRxiv*, 2019, preprint, DOI:10.26434/chemrxiv.10060262.v1.
- 35 W. Rock, B. Qiao, T. Zhou, A. E. Clark and A. Uysal, Heavy Anionic Complex Creates a Unique Water Structure at a Soft Charged Interface, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2018, **122**, 29228–29236.
- 36 Y. Mao, O. Demerdash, M. Head-Gordon and T. Head-Gordon, Assessing ion–water interactions in the amoeba force field using energy decomposition analysis of electronic structure calculations, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2016, **12**, 5422–5437.
- 37 D. Frenkel and B. Smit, *Understanding molecular simulation: from algorithms to applications*, Elsevier, 2001, vol. 1.
- 38 B. Chen, J. I. Siepmann and M. L. Klein, Vapor–Liquid interfacial properties of mutually saturated water/1-butanol solutions, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2002, **124**, 12232–12237.
- 39 J. L. Chen, B. Xue, D. B. Harwood, Q. P. Chen, C. J. Peters and J. I. Siepmann, A Monte Carlo simulation study of the interfacial tension for water/oil mixtures at elevated temperatures and pressures: Water/n-dodecane, water/toluene, and water/(n-dodecane+ toluene), *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 2018, **476**, 16–24.
- 40 J. T. Kindt, Accounting for finite-number effects on cluster size distributions in simulations of equilibrium aggregation, *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation*, 2012, **9**, 147–152.
- 41 L. A. Patel and J. T. Kindt, Cluster Free Energies from Simple Simulations of Small Numbers of Aggregants: Nucleation of Liquid MTBE from Vapor and Aqueous Phases, *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation*, 2017, **13**, 1023–1033.
- 42 X. Zhang, L. Patel, O. Beckwith, R. Schneider, C. Weeden and J. Kindt, Extracting aggregation free energies of mixed clusters from simulations of small systems: application to ionic surfactant micelles, *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation*, 2017, **13**, 5195–5206.
- 43 X. Zhang, J. G. A. Nunez and J. T. Kindt, Derivation of micelle size-dependent free energies of aggregation for octyl phosphocholine from molecular dynamics simulation, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 2019, **485**, 83–93.
- 44 M. J. Servis, D. T. Wu, J. C. Shafer and A. E. Clark, Reimagining Third Phase Formation as the Miscibility Gap of a Molecular Solution, *ChemRxiv*, 2019, preprint, DOI:10.26434/chemrxiv.10060253.v1.
- 45 Y. I. Yang, Q. Shao, J. Zhang, L. Yang and Y. Q. Gao, Enhanced sampling in molecular dynamics, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2019, **151**, 070902.
- 46 Y. Miao and J. A. McCammon, Unconstrained enhanced sampling for free energy calculations of biomolecules: a review, *Molecular simulation*, 2016, **42**, 1046–1055.
- 47 C. R. Weinberger and G. J. Tucker, *Multiscale materials modeling for nanomechanics*, Springer, 2016.
- 48 R. G. Mullen, J.-E. Shea and B. Peters, Transmission coefficients, committers, and solvent coordinates in ion-pair dissociation, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2014, **10**, 659–667.
- 49 T. Zhou, E. Martinez-Baez, G. Schenter and A. E. Clark, PageRank as a collective variable to study complex chemical transformations and their energy landscapes, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2019, **150**, 134102.
- 50 R. W. Zwanzig, High-temperature equation of state by a perturbation method. I. Nonpolar gases, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1954, **22**, 1420–1426.
- 51 C. H. Bennett, Efficient Estimate of Free Energy Differences from Monte Carlo Data, *The journal of Computational Physics*, 1976, **22**, 245–268.
- 52 M. R. Shirts and J. D. Chodera, Statistically optimal analysis of samples from multiple equilibrium states, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2008, **129**, 124105.
- 53 M. Mezei and D. Beveridge, Free energy simulations, *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1986, **482**, 1–23.
- 54 M. Mezei, S. Swaminathan and D. L. Beveridge, Ab initio calculation of the free energy of liquid water, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 1978, **100**, 3255–3256.
- 55 M. R. Mruzik, F. F. Abraham, D. E. Schreiber and G. Pound, A Monte Carlo study of ion–water clusters, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1976, **64**, 481–491.
- 56 N. Bhatnagar, G. Kamath, I. Chelst and J. J. Potoff, Direct calculation of 1-octanol–water partition coefficients from adaptive biasing force molecular dynamics simulations, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2012, **137**, 014502.
- 57 C. C. Bannan, G. Calabró, D. Y. Kyu and D. L. Mobley, Calculating partition coefficients of small molecules in octanol/water and cyclohexane/water, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2016, **12**, 4015–4024.
- 58 A. S. Paluch, S. Jayaraman, J. K. Shah and E. J. Maginn, A method for computing the solubility limit of solids: Application to sodium chloride in water and alcohols, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2010, **133**, 124504.
- 59 B. Peters, G. T. Beckham and B. L. Trout, Extensions to the likelihood maximization approach for finding reaction coordinates, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2007, **127**, 034109.
- 60 P. L. Geissler, C. Dellago and D. Chandler, Kinetic pathways of ion pair dissociation in water, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 1999, **103**, 3706–3710.
- 61 S. Roy, M. D. Baer, C. J. Mundy and G. K. Schenter, Marcus theory of ion-pairing, *Journal of chemical theory and computation*, 2017, **13**, 3470–3477.
- 62 Y. Yonetani, Solvent-coordinate free-energy landscape view of water-mediated ion-pair dissociation, *Molecular Physics*, 2017, **115**, 2987–2998.
- 63 G. Ciccotti, M. Ferrario, J. T. Hynes and R. Kapral, Dynamics of ion pair interconversion in a polar solvent, *The Journal of*

- chemical physics*, 1990, **93**, 7137–7147.
- 64 A. Carof, M. Salanne, T. Charpentier and B. Rotenberg, Collective water dynamics in the first solvation shell drive the NMR relaxation of aqueous quadrupolar cations, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2016, **145**, 124508.
- 65 N. Kikkawa, L. Wang and A. Morita, Microscopic barrier mechanism of ion transport through liquid–liquid interface, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2015, **137**, 8022–8025.
- 66 N. Kikkawa, L. Wang and A. Morita, Computational study of effect of water finger on ion transport through water-oil interface, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2016, **145**, 014702.
- 67 P. V. Banushkina and S. V. Krivov, Nonparametric variational optimization of reaction coordinates, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2015, **143**, 11B607_1.
- 68 W. Li and A. Ma, Recent developments in methods for identifying reaction coordinates, *Molecular simulation*, 2014, **40**, 784–793.
- 69 T. Takayanagi, T. Nakatomi and Y. Yonetani, On the ion-pair dissociation mechanisms in the small NaCl·(H₂O)₆ cluster: A perspective from reaction path search calculations, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2018, **39**, 1835–1842.
- 70 A. Ma and A. R. Dinner, Automatic method for identifying reaction coordinates in complex systems, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2005, **109**, 6769–6779.
- 71 Y. Mu, P. H. Nguyen and G. Stock, Energy landscape of a small peptide revealed by dihedral angle principal component analysis, *Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics*, 2005, **58**, 45–52.
- 72 P. Das, M. Moll, H. Stamati, L. E. Kavragi and C. Clementi, Low-dimensional, free-energy landscapes of protein-folding reactions by nonlinear dimensionality reduction, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2006, **103**, 9885–9890.
- 73 M. Ceriotti, G. A. Tribello and M. Parrinello, Simplifying the representation of complex free-energy landscapes using sketch-map, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2011, **108**, 13023–13028.
- 74 N. Galamba, Water’s structure around hydrophobic solutes and the iceberg model, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2013, **117**, 2153–2159.
- 75 P.-L. Chau and A. Hardwick, A new order parameter for tetrahedral configurations, *Molecular Physics*, 1998, **93**, 511–518.
- 76 N. Giovambattista, P. G. Debenedetti, F. Sciortino and H. E. Stanley, Structural order in glassy water, *Physical Review E*, 2005, **71**, 061505.
- 77 D. R. Nutt and J. C. Smith, Dual function of the hydration layer around an antifreeze protein revealed by atomistic molecular dynamics simulations, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2008, **130**, 13066–13073.
- 78 M. Paolantoni, N. F. Lago, M. Albertí and A. Laganà, Tetrahedral ordering in water: Raman profiles and their temperature dependence, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A*, 2009, **113**, 15100–15105.
- 79 D. Nayar and C. Chakravarty, Water and water-like liquids: Relationships between structure, entropy and mobility, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2013, **15**, 14162–14177.
- 80 F. Sedlmeier, D. Horinek and R. R. Netz, Spatial correlations of density and structural fluctuations in liquid water: A comparative simulation study, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2011, **133**, 1391–1398.
- 81 E. Duboué-Dijon and D. Laage, Characterization of the local structure in liquid water by various order parameters, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2015, **119**, 8406–8418.
- 82 J. D. Bernal, A geometrical approach to the structure of liquids, *Nature*, 1959, **183**, 141–147.
- 83 N. Medvedev, V. Voloshin and Y. I. Naberukhin, Structure of simple liquids as a problem of percolation in the Voronoi grid, *Journal of Structural Chemistry*, 1989, **30**, 253–260.
- 84 Y. I. Naberukhin, V. Voloshin and N. Medvedev, Geometrical analysis of the structure of simple liquids: percolation approach, *Molecular Physics*, 1991, **73**, 917–936.
- 85 A. Idrissi, P. Damay, K. Yukichi and P. Jedlovsky, Self-association of urea in aqueous solutions: A Voronoi polyhedron analysis study, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2008, **129**, 164512.
- 86 G. E. Carlsson, R. L. Cohen, W.-C. Hsiang and J. D. Jones, *Algebraic topology and its applications*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2012, vol. 27.
- 87 H. E. Stanley and J. Teixeira, Interpretation of the Unusual Behavior of H₂O and D₂O at Low Temperatures: Tests of a Percolation Model, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1980, **73**, 3404–3422.
- 88 F. W. Starr, J. K. Nielsen and H. E. Stanley, Fast and slow dynamics of hydrogen bonds in liquid water, *Physical Review Letters*, 1999, **82**, 2294.
- 89 B. L. Mooney, L. R. Corrales and A. E. Clark, Novel analysis of cation solvation using a graph theoretic approach, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2012, **116**, 4263–4275.
- 90 R. Solomonoff and A. Rapoport, Connectivity of Random Nets, *The bulletin of mathematical biophysics*, 1951, **13**, 107–117.
- 91 P. Erdős and A. Rényi, On Random Graphs I., *Publicationes Mathematicae*, 1959, **6**, 290–297.
- 92 S. H. Chen, J. Rouch, F. Sciortino and P. Tartaglia, Static and Dynamic Properties of Water-in-Oil Microemulsions Near the Critical and Percolation Points, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 1994, **6**, 10855–10883.
- 93 F. Mallamace, R. Beneduci, P. Gambadauro, D. Lombardo and S. Chen, Glass and percolation transitions in dense attractive micellar system, *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 2001, **302**, 202–219.
- 94 A. E. Clark, M. J. Servis, Z. Liu, E. Martinez-Baez, J. Su, E. R. Batista, P. Yang, A. Wildman, T. Stetina, X. Li, K. Newcomb, E. J. Maginn, J. Autschbach and D. A. Dixon, *Ion Exchange and Solvent Extraction*, CRC Press, 2019, vol. 23, ch. Solvent Extraction through the Lens of Advanced Modeling and Simulation, pp. 147–218.
- 95 A. E. Clark, J. Braley and P. Yang, *Experimental and Theoret-*

- ical Approaches to Actinide Chemistry*, Wiley, 2018.
- 96 M. Hudelson, B. L. Mooney and A. E. Clark, Determining polyhedral arrangements of atoms using PageRank, *Journal of Mathematical Chemistry*, 2012, **50**, 2342–2350.
 - 97 C.-H. Wang, P. Bai, J. I. Siepmann and A. E. Clark, Deconstructing hydrogen-bond networks in confined nanoporous materials: implications for alcohol–water separation, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2014, **118**, 19723–19732.
 - 98 P. Zhao, S. M. Nackman and C. K. Law, On the application of betweenness centrality in chemical network analysis: Computational diagnostics and model reduction, *Combustion and Flame*, 2015, **162**, 2991–2998.
 - 99 L. E. Edens, S. Pednekar, J. F. Morris, G. K. Schenter, A. E. Clark and J. Chun, Global topology of contact force networks: Insight into shear thickening suspensions, *Physical Review E*, 2019, **99**, 012607.
 - 100 V. D. Blondel, J.-L. Guillaume, R. Lambiotte and E. Lefebvre, Fast unfolding of communities in large networks, *Journal of statistical mechanics: theory and experiment*, 2008, **2008**, P10008.
 - 101 J. R. Munkres, *Elements of algebraic topology*. 1984.
 - 102 R. Ghrist, Barcodes: The persistent topology of data, *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society*, 2008, **45**, 61–75.
 - 103 K. Xia and G. W. Wei, Persistent homology analysis of protein structure, flexibility, and folding, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Biomedical Engineering*, 2014, **30**, 814–844.
 - 104 K. Xia, Persistent homology analysis of ion aggregations and hydrogen-bonding networks, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2018, **20**, 13448–13460.
 - 105 M. Pouvreau, M. Dembowski, S. B. Clark, J. G. Reynolds, K. M. Rosso, G. K. Schenter, C. I. Pearce and A. E. Clark, Ab Initio Molecular Dynamics Reveal Spectroscopic Siblings and Ion Pairing as New Challenges for Elucidating Prenucleation Aluminum Speciation, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2018, **122**, 7394–7402.
 - 106 J. M. Stubbs and J. I. Siepmann, Elucidating the vibrational spectra of hydrogen-bonded aggregates in solution: Electronic structure calculations with implicit solvent and first-principles molecular dynamics simulations with explicit solvent for 1-hexanol in n-hexane, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2005, **127**, 4722–4729.
 - 107 Y. Liu, J. Tossell and H. Nekvasil, A theoretical study of structural factors correlated with ²³Na NMR parameters, *American Mineralogist*, 2004, **89**, 1314–1322.
 - 108 R. Creekmore and C. Reilley, Nuclear magnetic resonance determination of hydration numbers of electrolytes in concentrated aqueous solutions, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 1969, **73**, 1563–1568.
 - 109 E. R. Malinowski, P. S. Knapp and B. Feuer, NMR studies of aqueous electrolyte solutions. I. Hydration number of NaCl determined from temperature effects on proton shift, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 1966, **45**, 4274–4279.
 - 110 E. Martinez-Baez, R. Feng, C. I. Pearce, G. K. Schenter and A. E. Clark, ²⁷Al NMR chemical shift of Al(OH)₄⁻ from first principles. Assessment of error cancellation in NMR chemical shift computations in chemically distinct reference and targeted systems, *arXiv*, 2019, preprint arXiv:2001.00107v1.
 - 111 T. R. Graham, M. Dembowski, E. Martinez-Baez, X. Zhang, N. R. Jaegers, J. Hu, M. S. Gruszkiewicz, H.-W. Wang, A. G. Stack, M. E. Bowden *et al.*, In Situ 27Al NMR Spectroscopy of Aluminate in Sodium Hydroxide Solutions above and below Saturation with Respect to Gibbsite, *Inorganic chemistry*, 2018, **57**, 11864–11873.
 - 112 A. Wildman, E. Martinez-Baez, J. Fulton, G. Schenter, C. Pearce, A. E. Clark and X. Li, Anticorrelated contributions to pre-edge features of aluminate near-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy in concentrated electrolytes, *The journal of physical chemistry letters*, 2018, **9**, 2444–2449.
 - 113 K. Henzler, E. O. Fetisov, M. Galib, M. D. Baer, B. A. Legg, C. Borca, J. M. Xto, S. Pin, J. L. Fulton, G. K. Schenter *et al.*, Supersaturated calcium carbonate solutions are classical, *Science advances*, 2018, **4**, eaao6283.
 - 114 B. Chen and J. I. Siepmann, Improving the Efficiency of the Aggregation- Volume- Bias Monte Carlo Algorithm, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2001, **105**, 11275–11282.
 - 115 M. Hellström and J. Behler, Structure of aqueous NaOH solutions: insights from neural-network-based molecular dynamics simulations, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2017, **19**, 82–96.
 - 116 I. Bakó, T. Megyes, S. Bálint, T. Grósz and V. Chihaiia, Water–Methanol mixtures: topology of hydrogen bonded network, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2008, **10**, 5004–5011.
 - 117 L. Dougan, S. Bates, R. Hargreaves, J. Fox, J. Crain, J. Finney, V. Reat and A. Soper, Methanol-water solutions: A bi-percolating liquid mixture, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2004, **121**, 6456–6462.
 - 118 A. Perera and B. Kežić, Fluctuations and micro-heterogeneity in mixtures of complex liquids, *Faraday Discussions*, 2013, **167**, 145–158.
 - 119 B. Kežić and A. Perera, Aqueous tert-butanol mixtures: a model for molecular-emulsions, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2012, **137**, 014501.
 - 120 B. Kežić and A. Perera, Revisiting aqueous-acetone mixtures through the concept of molecular emulsions, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2012, **137**, 134502.
 - 121 B. Kežić, R. Mazighi and A. Perera, A model for molecular emulsions: Water and weak water mixtures, *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 2013, **392**, 567–582.
 - 122 A. Perera, Molecular emulsions: from charge order to domain order, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2017, **19**, 28275–28285.
 - 123 T. N. Zemb, M. Klossek, T. Lopian, J. Marcus, S. Schöetl, D. Horinek, S. F. Prevost, D. Touraud, O. Diat, S. Marčelja *et al.*, How to explain microemulsions formed by solvent mixtures without conventional surfactants, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2016, **113**, 4260–4265.

- 124 S. Schoettl, J. Marcus, O. Diat, D. Touraud, W. Kunz, T. Zemb and D. Horinek, Emergence of surfactant-free micelles from ternary solutions, *Chemical Science*, 2014, **5**, 2949–2954.
- 125 M. Kelley, A. Donley, S. Clark and A. Clark, Structure and dynamics of NaCl ion pairing in solutions of water and methanol, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2015, **119**, 15652–15661.
- 126 M. P. Kelley, P. Yang, S. B. Clark and A. E. Clark, Structural and thermodynamic properties of the CmIII ion solvated by water and methanol, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 2016, **55**, 4992–4999.
- 127 M. P. Kelley, P. Yang, S. B. Clark and A. E. Clark, Competitive Interactions Within Cm (III) Solvation in Binary Water/Methanol Solutions, *Inorganic chemistry*, 2018, **57**, 10050–10058.
- 128 A. Oleinikova, I. Brovchenko, A. Geiger and B. Guillot, Percolation of water in aqueous solution and liquid–liquid immiscibility, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 2002, **117**, 3296–3304.
- 129 L. B. Pártay, P. Jedlovsky, I. Brovchenko and A. Oleinikova, Formation of mesoscopic water networks in aqueous systems, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2007, **9**, 1341–1346.
- 130 R. S. Taylor and B. C. Garrett, Accommodation of alcohols by the liquid/vapor interface of water: Molecular dynamics study, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 1999, **103**, 844–851.
- 131 E. A. Raymond, T. L. Tarbuck, M. G. Brown and G. L. Richmond, Hydrogen-bonding interactions at the vapor/water interface investigated by vibrational sum-frequency spectroscopy of HOD/H₂O/D₂O mixtures and molecular dynamics simulations, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2003, **107**, 546–556.
- 132 D. S. Walker and G. L. Richmond, Depth Profiling of Water Molecules at the Liquid- Liquid Interface Using a Combined Surface Vibrational Spectroscopy and Molecular Dynamics Approach, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2007, **129**, 9446–9451.
- 133 M. Sulpizi, M. Salanne, M. Sprik and M.-P. Gaigeot, Vibrational sum frequency generation spectroscopy of the water liquid–vapor interface from density functional theory-based molecular dynamics simulations, *The journal of physical chemistry letters*, 2012, **4**, 83–87.
- 134 S. J. Marrink, M. Berkowitz and H. J. Berendsen, Molecular dynamics simulation of a membrane/water interface: the ordering of water and its relation to the hydration force, *Langmuir*, 1993, **9**, 3122–3131.
- 135 A. Pohorille and I. Benjamin, Molecular dynamics of phenol at the liquid–vapor interface of water, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 1991, **94**, 5599–5605.
- 136 T. Zhou, A. McCue, Y. Ghadar, I. Bakolaj and A. E. Clark, Structural and Dynamic Heterogeneity of Capillary Wave Fronts at Aqueous Interfaces, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2017, **121**, 9052–9062.
- 137 L. B. Pártay, G. Hantal, P. Jedlovsky, Á. Vincze and G. Horvai, A new method for determining the interfacial molecules and characterizing the surface roughness in computer simulations. Application to the liquid–vapor interface of water, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2008, **29**, 945–956.
- 138 G. Hantal, M. Darvas, L. B. Partay, G. Horvai and P. Jedlovsky, Molecular level properties of the free water surface and different organic liquid/water interfaces, as seen from ITIM analysis of computer simulation results, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 2010, **22**, 284112.
- 139 M. Segal, S. S. Kantorovich, P. Jedlovsky and M. Jorge, The Generalized Identification of Truly Interfacial Molecules (Itim) Algorithm for Nonplanar Interfaces, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, 044110.
- 140 M. J. Servis and A. E. Clark, Surfactant-enhanced heterogeneity of the aqueous interface drives water extraction into organic solvents, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2019, **21**, 2866–2874.
- 141 D. E. Otten, P. R. Shaffer, P. L. Geissler and R. J. Saykally, Elucidating the Mechanism of Selective Ion Adsorption to the Liquid Water Surface, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2012, **109**, 701–705.
- 142 V. Venkateshwaran, S. Vembanur and S. Garde, Water-Mediated Ion–Ion Interactions are Enhanced at the Water Vapor–Liquid Interface, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2014, **111**, 8729–8734.
- 143 Y. Wang, S. Sinha, P. R. Desai, H. Jing and S. Das, Ion at Air-Water Interface Enhances Capillary Wave Fluctuations: Energetics of Ion Adsorption, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 2018, **140**, 12853–12861.
- 144 I. Benjamin, Theory and Computer Simulations of Solvation and Chemical Reactions at Liquid Interfaces, *Accounts of Chemical Research*, 1995, **28**, 233–239.
- 145 M. Baaden, M. Burgard and G. Wipff, TBP at the water- oil interface: the effect of TBP concentration and water acidity investigated by molecular dynamics simulations, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2001, **105**, 11131–11141.
- 146 N. Sieffert and G. Wipff, The [BMI][Tf₂N] ionic liquid/water binary system: A molecular dynamics study of phase separation and of the liquid- liquid interface, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2006, **110**, 13076–13085.
- 147 K. J. Schweighofer and I. Benjamin, Transfer of small ions across the water/1, 2-dichloroethane interface, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 1995, **99**, 9974–9985.
- 148 J. J. Karnes and I. Benjamin, Geometric and energetic considerations of surface fluctuations during ion transfer across the water-immiscible organic liquid interface, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 2016, **145**, 014701.
- 149 J. J. Karnes, N. Villavicencio and I. Benjamin, Transfer of an Erbium Ion across the Water/Dodecane Interface: Structure and Thermodynamics via Molecular Dynamics Simulations, *Chemical Physics Letters*, 2019, 136825.
- 150 I. Benjamin, Hydronium ion at the water/1, 2-dichloroethane interface: Structure, thermodynamics, and dynamics of ion transfer, *The Journal of chemical*

- physics, 2019, **151**, 094701.
- 151 J. Rydberg, M. Cox, C. Musikas and G. Choppin, *Solvent Extraction Principles and Practices*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 2nd edn, 2004.
 - 152 K. Nash and G. Choppin, *Separations Chemistry for Actinide Elements: Recent Developments and Historical Perspective*, *Separation Science and Technology*, 1997, **34**, 255–274.
 - 153 K. Nash and J. Braley, *Advanced Separation Techniques for Nuclear Fuel Reprocessing Waste Treatment*, Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy, Cambridge, UK, 2011, pp. 3–22.
 - 154 E. Scoppola, E. Watkins, G. Li Destri, L. Porcar, R. A. Campbell, O. Kononov, G. Fragneto, and O. Diat, Structure of a liquid/liquid interface during solvent extraction combining X-ray and neutron reflectivity measurements., *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2015, **17**, 15093–15097.
 - 155 L. Soderholm, S. Skanthakumar and R. E. Wilson, Structural correspondence between uranyl chloride complexes in solution and their stability constants., *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A*, 2011, **115**, 4959–4967.
 - 156 K. El Hage, R. J. Bemish and M. Meuwly, From in silica to in silico: retention thermodynamics at solid–liquid interfaces, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2018, **20**, 18610–18622.
 - 157 S. M. Melnikov, A. Hořlitzel, A. Seidel-Morgenstern and U. Tallarek, A Molecular Dynamics View on Hydrophilic Interaction Chromatography with Polar-Bonded Phases: Properties of the Water-Rich Layer at a Silica Surface Modified with Diol-Functionalized Alkyl Chains, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2016, **120**, 13126–13138.
 - 158 R. K. Lindsey, J. L. Rafferty, B. L. Eggimann, J. I. Siepmann and M. R. Schure, Molecular simulation studies of reversed-phase liquid chromatography, *Journal of Chromatography A*, 2013, **1287**, 60–82.
 - 159 E. National Academies of Sciences and Medicine., *A Research Agenda for Transforming Separation Science.*, The National Academies Press., 2019.
 - 160 R. Guenther, D. Blahnik, T. Campbell, U. Jenquin, J. Mendel, L. Thomas and C. Thornhill, *Characterization of spent fuel approved testing material—ATM-105*, Pacific northwest lab., richland, wa (united states) technical report, 1991.
 - 161 J. Magill, V. Berthou, D. Haas, J. Galy, R. Schenkel, J. Wiese, G. Heusener, J. Tommasi and G. Youinou, Impact limits of partitioning and transmutation scenarios on the radiotoxicity of actinides in radioactive waste, *Nuclear Energy-London*, 2003, **42**, 263–278.
 - 162 R. Atta-Fynn, E. J. Bylaska and W. A. De Jong, Importance of counteranions on the hydration structure of the curium ion, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters*, 2013, **4**, 2166–2170.
 - 163 R. Atta-Fynn, E. J. Bylaska and de Jong. W, Strengthening of the Coordination Shell by Counter Ions in Aqueous Th 4+ Solutions, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A*, 2016, **120**, 10216–10222.
 - 164 S. Nagasaki, K. Kinoshita, Y. Enokida and A. Suzuki, Solvent extraction of Np (V) with CMPO from nitric acid solutions containing U (VI), *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, 1992, **29**, 1100–1107.
 - 165 J. C. Sullivan, A. J. Zielen and J. C. Hindman, Specific Interaction between Np(V) and U(VI) in Aqueous Perchloric Acid Media., *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 1961, **83**, 3373–3378.
 - 166 J. C. Sullivan, Complex Ion Formation between Cations - Spectra and Identification of a Np(V)-Cr(III) Complex., *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 1962, **84**, 4256–4259.
 - 167 J. W. Freiderich, A. G. Burn, L. R. Martin, K. L. Nash and A. E. Clark, A Combined Density Functional Theory and Spectrophotometry Study of the Bonding Interactions of [NpO₂U⁴⁺] Cation–Cation Complexes, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 2017, **56**, 4788–4795.
 - 168 S. J. Keasler, J. L. Lewin, J. I. Siepmann, N. M. Gryska, R. B. Ross, N. E. Schultz and M. Nakamura, Molecular insights for the optimization of solvent-based selective extraction of ethanol from fermentation broths, *AIChE Journal*, 2013, **59**, 3065–3070.
 - 169 S. J. Keasler, P. Bai, M. Tsapatsis and J. I. Siepmann, Concentration effects on the selective extraction of ethanol from aqueous solution using silicalite-1 and decanol isomers, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 2014, **362**, 118–124.
 - 170 M. Špadina, K. Bohinc, T. Zemb and J.-F. Dufrêche, Multi-component Model for the Prediction of Nuclear Waste/Rare-Earth Extraction Processes, *Langmuir*, 2018, **34**, 10434–10447.
 - 171 M. Špadina, K. Bohinc, T. Zemb and J.-F. Dufrêche, Colloidal Model for the Prediction of the Extraction of Rare Earths Assisted by the Acidic Extractant, *Langmuir*, 2019, **35**, 3215–3230.
 - 172 A. Karmakar, M. Duvail, M. Bley, T. Zemb and J.-F. Dufrêche, Combined supramolecular and mesoscale modelling of liquid–liquid extraction of rare earth salts, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2018, **555**, 713–727.
 - 173 K. Osseo-Asare, Aggregation, reversed micelles, and microemulsions in liquid-liquid extraction: the tri-n-butyl phosphatediluent-water-electrolyte system, *Advances in colloid and interface science*, 1991, **37**, 123–173.
 - 174 R. Motokawa, S. Suzuki, H. Ogawa, M. Antonio and T. Yaita, Microscopic Structures of Tri-n-butyl Phosphate/n-Octane Mixtures by X-ray and Neutron Scattering in a Wide q Range, *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2012, **116**, 1319–1327.
 - 175 M. J. Servis, C. A. Tormey, D. T. Wu and J. C. Braley, A Molecular Dynamics Study of Tributyl Phosphate and Di-amyl Amyl Phosphonate Self-Aggregation in Dodecane and Octane, *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2016, **120**, 2796–2806.
 - 176 Q. N. Vo, C. A. Hawkins, L. X. Dang, M. Nilsson and H. D. Nguyen, Computational study of molecular structure and self-association of tri-n-butyl phosphates in n-dodecane, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2015, **119**, 1588–1597.
 - 177 J. Mu, R. Motokawa, C. Williams, K. Akutsu, S. Nishitsuji

- and A. Masters, Comparative Molecular Dynamics Study on Tri-n-butyl Phosphate in Organic and Aqueous Environments and Its Relevance to Nuclear Extraction Processes, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2016, **120**, 5183–5193.
- 178 A. Baldwin, M. Servis, Y. Yang, N. Bridges, D. Wu and J. Shafer, The Structure of Tributyl Phosphate Solutions: Nitric Acid, Uranium (VI), and Zirconium (IV), *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 2017, **246**, 225–235.
- 179 J. Mu, R. Motokawa, K. Akutsu, S. Nishitsuji and A. Masters, A Novel Micro-Emulsion Phase Transition: Towards the elucidation of Third Phase Formation in Spent Nuclear Fuel Reprocessing, *Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2018, **122**, 1439–1452.
- 180 R. J. Ellis, Y. Meridiano, J. Muller, L. Berthon, P. Guilbaud, N. Zorz, M. R. Antonio, T. Demars and T. Zemb, Complexation-Induced Supramolecular Assembly Drives Metal-Ion Extraction, *Chemistry–A European Journal*, 2014, **20**, 12796–12807.
- 181 B. Qiao, T. Demars, M. Olvera de la Cruz and R. J. Ellis, How hydrogen bonds affect the growth of reverse micelles around coordinating metal ions, *The journal of physical chemistry letters*, 2014, **5**, 1440–1444.
- 182 B. Qiao, G. Ferru and R. J. Ellis, Complexation Enhancement Drives Water-to-Oil Ion Transport: A Simulation Study, *Chemistry–A European Journal*, 2017, **23**, 427–436.
- 183 P. Guilbaud, L. Berthon, W. Louisfremea, O. Diat and N. Zorz, Determination of the Structures of Uranyl–Tri-n-butyl-Phosphate Aggregates by Coupling Experimental Results with Molecular Dynamic Simulations, *Chemistry–A European Journal*, 2017, **23**, 16660–16670.
- 184 R. Motokawa, T. Kobayashi, H. Endo, J. Mu, C. D. Williams, A. J. Masters, M. R. Antonio, W. T. Heller and M. Nagao, A Telescoping View of Solute Architectures in a Complex Fluid System, *ACS Central Science*, 2018, **5**, 85–96.
- 185 R. Chiarizia, M. Jensen, M. Borkowski, J. Ferraro, P. Thiagarajan and K. Littrell, Third Phase Formation Revisited: The U(VI), HNO₃, TBP, n-Dodecane System, *Solvent Extraction and Ion Exchange*, 2003, **21**, 1–27.
- 186 K. A. Lovering, S. Nayak, W. Bu and A. Uysal, The Role of Specific Ion Effects in Ion Transport: The Case of Nitrate and Thiocyanate, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 2020.
- 187 R. Kusaka and M. Watanabe, The structure of a lanthanide complex at an extractant/water interface studied using heterodyne-detected vibrational sum frequency generation, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2018, **20**, 2809–2813.
- 188 R. Kusaka and M. Watanabe, Mechanism of phase transfer of uranyl ions: a vibrational sum frequency generation spectroscopy study on solvent extraction in nuclear reprocessing, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2018, **20**, 29588–29590.
- 189 Z. Liang, W. Bu, K. J. Schweighofer, D. J. Walwark, J. S. Harvey, G. R. Hanlon, D. Amoanu, C. Erol, I. Benjamin and M. L. Schlossman, Nanoscale view of assisted ion transport across the liquid–liquid interface, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2019, **116**, 18227–18232.
- 190 M. Buehl and G. Wipff, Insights into uranyl chemistry from molecular dynamics simulations, *ChemPhysChem*, 2011, **12**, 3095–3105.
- 191 G. Benay and G. Wipff, Liquid–Liquid extraction of uranyl by an amide ligand: interfacial features studied by MD and PMF simulations, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2013, **117**, 7399–7415.
- 192 G. Benay and G. Wipff, Liquid–Liquid Extraction of Uranyl by TBP: The TBP and ions models and related interfacial features revisited by MD and PMF simulations, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2014, **118**, 3133–3149.
- 193 X. Ye, S. Cui, V. d. Almeida and B. Khomami, Interfacial complex formation in uranyl extraction by tributyl phosphate in dodecane diluent: a molecular dynamics study, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 2009, **113**, 9852–9862.
- 194 X. Ye, S. Cui, V. F. de Almeida, B. P. Hay and B. Khomami, Uranyl nitrate complex extraction into TBP/dodecane organic solutions: a molecular dynamics study, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 2010, **12**, 15406–15409.
- 195 C. Den Auwer, C. Lecouteux, M. Charbonnel, C. Madic and R. Guillaumont, XAS study of actinide and lanthanide solvent extraction compounds. UO₂ (NO₃)₂ (TIBP)₂ and UO₂ (NO₃)₂ (TBP)₂ (with TIBP= tri-isobutylphosphate and TBP= tributylphosphate), *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2233–2238.
- 196 C. Den Auwer, M. Charbonnel, M. Presson, C. Madic and R. Guillaumont, Xas study of actinide solvent extraction compounds. ii: UO₂ (NO₃)₂ (L)₂ (with L= tri-isobutylphosphate, tri-n-butylphosphate, trimethylphosphate and triphenylphosphate), *Polyhedron*, 1998, **17**, 4507–4517.
- 197 L. B. Pártay, G. Hantal, P. Jedlovsky, Á. Vincze and G. Horvai, A new method for determining the interfacial molecules and characterizing the surface roughness in computer simulations. Application to the liquid–vapor interface of water, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2008, **29**, 945–956.
- 198 N. Kumar, M. J. Servis, Z. Liu and A. E. Clark, Competitive Interactions at Electrolyte/Octanol Interfaces - A Molecular Perspective, *ChemRxiv*, 2020, preprint, DOI: 10.26434/chemrxiv.11556132.

Solution Complexity: Coupled Length and Timescales of Multiple Components

Complex, multicomponent, liquids benefit from a hierarchical understanding of solution speciation, collective organization and dynamics.